

CS - MACH1

D2.1 – Preliminary Assessment Report

VLIZ

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List of referenced acronyms

CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CS-MACH1	MARine Citizen science data Horizon
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOVs	Essential ocean Variables
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biodiversity Information System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
Ifremer	French Institute for Ocean Science
JCDP	Joint Cetacean Data Protocol
MARIS	Marine Information Service, MARIS B.V.
MCS	Marine Citizen Science
MCSI	Marine Citizen Science Initiatives
MCSDN	Marine Citizen Science Data Network
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment
OTTERS	Social Transformation for Water Stewardship through Scaling Up Citizen Science
OutBe	OutBe S.R.L.
SCOOP	Solutions for Cost-effective Ocean Observation Platform
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SMHI	Swedish and Meteorological Institute
SSBE	SeaScape Belgium
VLIZ	Flanders Marine Institute
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Context of WP2 within the CS-MACH1 project

The **CS-MACH1** project aims to strengthen the role of **marine and coastal citizen science initiatives (MCSI)** in Europe's ocean observation and **data management** landscape. Citizen science contributes valuable complementary data to traditional monitoring programmes, enhancing spatial and temporal coverage while engaging society in ocean knowledge generation.

Within this broader framework, Work Package 2 (WP2) focuses on understanding how MCSI currently manages their data, from collection and storage to sharing and long-term accessibility. The ultimate goal is to identify common practices, gaps, and challenges, and to provide a factual evidence base for improving dataflow, interoperability and FAIR data stewardship across the European MCSI community. **FAIR data** refers to data that are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable: a set of guiding principles that ensure data can be easily discovered, properly accessed under clear conditions, combined with other datasets, and reused for future research and applications.

1.2. Objectives and scope of this deliverable 2.1

This deliverable, **D2.1 – Preliminary Assessment Report**, provides an empirical overview of how MCSI **handle** their data today, based on responses to a structured, Europe-wide survey distributed to 1,233 identified initiatives. The deliverable maps the current landscape of data-related practices and identifies early trends, barriers, and capacity needs.

It captures, for the first time, a consolidated view of how marine and coastal citizen science initiatives across Europe and neighbouring countries **organise, manage, and share** their data. The focus lies on understanding the present situation, not yet on developing recommendations or technical solutions.

Specifically, this deliverable aims to:

- Characterise the diversity of data management related practices within MCSI across Europe and neighbouring countries;
- Identify strengths, challenges, and barriers in the way these initiatives acquire, manage, and disseminate data.

The analysis presented here is derived exclusively from the survey conducted among the identified initiatives. While the dataset may not represent the entire European landscape exhaustively, it offers a comprehensive first snapshot of how data are currently handled in practice within marine and coastal citizen science.

2. Methodology

2.1. Overview

The methodological framework of D2.1 was designed to produce a comprehensive and representative preliminary assessment of data management practices among marine and coastal citizen science initiatives in Europe and neighbouring countries. The approach consisted of three main phases:

- Compilation of a database of relevant initiatives through the integration of existing European citizen science and marine data infrastructures;
- Design and dissemination of a structured survey to collect information on current data practices;
- Systematic processing and analysis of survey responses to identify trends, challenges, and capacity needs.

The methodology ensures transparency, reproducibility, and compliance with Horizon Europe's standards for open and responsible research.

2.2. Rationale for a survey approach

Given the fragmented and diverse nature of the marine citizen science community across Europe, a **survey-based approach** was identified as the most effective way to gather **standardised** and **comparable** information from a large number of initiatives. The survey captures both quantitative data, providing measurable indicators of current practices, and qualitative insights through open-ended questions that reveal the context behind those practices.

This approach allows WP2 to:

- Map the current landscape of data-handling and sharing within MCSI;
- Identify common bottlenecks in achieving FAIR and interoperable data flows;
- Collect evidence-based input for designing the qualitative phase.

The qualitative component of WP2 will build directly on this survey. Through interviews, it will delve deeper into the social, institutional, and technical factors influencing data management. Together, these two complementary phases will form a **mixed-methods assessment**, moving from mapping what exists to understanding why it exists and how it can be improved.

2.3. Compilation of the project database

VLIZ developed a consolidated database of **1,233 Marine and Coastal Citizen Science Initiatives (MCSI)** operating in Europe and neighbouring countries (hereafter referred to as European MCSI).

This database was created by merging and harmonising information from seven infrastructures and projects identified in the CS-MACH1 proposal, alongside other individual initiatives that were subsequently added to the contact list:

- WaveLinks: repository that served as the baseline for the list.
- OTTERS: their dataset was merged with WaveLinks.
- The following structures were contacted to provide input on marine citizen science projects: SCOOP, Cos4Cloud, CitSci-X, ECSA and Blue-Cloud.

2.4. Target population and inclusion criteria

The survey targeted citizen science initiatives with a marine, coastal, or estuarine focus. To be included, an initiative had to meet all the following criteria:

- Actively collect or generate data through citizen participation;
- Make use of some form of technology, tools, or sensors to support data collection or engagement;
- Operate within marine or coastal environments in Europe and neighboring countries;
- Maintain publicly accessible information (e.g. website, description, or contact details);
- Self-identify as a citizen science initiative or an organisation employing citizen science approaches.

This approach ensures that the assessment reflects the operational reality of projects directly contributing to marine data generation and sharing.

2.5. Survey design and distribution

The questionnaire was developed using Google Forms and structured around thematic sections reflecting the **full data lifecycle** and associated challenges. It combined closed-ended questions (single- and multiple-choice) with open-ended fields to capture context and nuance.

The survey was distributed by email to the 1,233 identified initiatives. The collection period lasted approximately two weeks, during which a single reminder was sent to maximise participation.

Responses were automatically recorded and exported for analysis. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed that their contributions would be anonymised and presented in aggregate form.

2.6. Data processing and analysis

After closure, responses were downloaded, cleaned, and harmonised. Quantitative responses were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, distribution). All analyses were conducted by VLIZ.

2.7. Ethical considerations

The study complies fully with GDPR and Horizon Europe ethical requirements. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the survey, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their answers. No personal data were retained beyond optional contact details, which were stored securely on VLIZ infrastructure.

2.8. Limitations

While the survey provides a valuable first insight into the data practices of European MCSI, certain limitations must be acknowledged:

- Response bias: initiatives with more developed data infrastructures may have been more inclined to complete the survey;
- Language constraint: the survey was conducted in English only;
- Self-reporting: results rely on participants' own descriptions of practice;
- Coverage: some small or emerging initiatives may not have been captured in the original database.

3. Survey structure

This chapter provides an overview of the structure and internal logic of the WP2 survey instrument.

The questionnaire was developed by VLIZ, in close consultation with all WP2 partners (SMHI, ECSA, OutBe, MARIS, SSBE, Ifremer, CSIC, CMCC), to obtain a structured and comparable overview of how marine and coastal citizen science initiatives (MCSI) in Europe and neighbouring countries currently manage and share their data. The survey combines factual multiple-choice items with selective open questions to capture both the diversity and the depth of practices in data acquisition, management, sharing, and capacity needs. The survey is composed of four thematic sections, followed by a short closing block.

3.1. Section 1: General characteristics of the project

Purpose

This section gathers contextual information to profile each participating initiative. These descriptors enable stratified analysis (e.g. by region, maturity, or topic) and ensure that subsequent results can be interpreted in context.

Topics covered

- Identification: project name, coordinator, website, contact details.
- Data collection technology: use of sensors, mobile applications, online tools, or manual recording.
- Geographical scope: country and region of activity, marine basin.
- Temporal dimension: start and end year of the initiative.
- Scale and participation: approximate number of participants per year, type of participants (wider public, divers, tourists, students, ...).
- Operational pattern: frequency of activities or events.
- Main thematic focus: e.g. biodiversity, litter, water quality, habitats.

Expected

insights

A clear **typology of initiatives** (national vs. transnational, long-running vs. new, thematic clusters) that will contextualise all subsequent findings.

3.2. Section 2: Data flow

Purpose

To capture how citizen science data are currently handled, from **storage** to **accessibility** and **hosting platforms**, thereby mapping the existing *as-is* data lifecycle.

Topics covered

- Experience with data management: whether projects possess relevant expertise.
- Data storage: where and how data are stored (e.g. locally, within institutional systems, or using external/cloud storage).
- Standardisation of data and metadata: whether the data are raw, converted, partially converted, or unknown.
- FAIR awareness: familiarity with the FAIR principles and their practical implementation.
- Use of best practices: adoption of standard methods, guidelines, or protocols for data management.
- Findability of the data: whether the project's data are findable, and if so, where/
- Accessibility of the data: where and to whom the data are accessible (only to the respondent, within their institution, to project partners, or publicly).
- Hosting platforms: repositories or databases used for publication and connections to infrastructures such as [OBIS](#), [EMODnet](#), or [GBIF](#).
- Recognition systems: mechanisms for tracking, attribution, or providing feedback to participating citizens (formally, informally, or not at all).

Expected insights

A baseline understanding of technological diversity, maturity in data stewardship, and existing gaps in the application of FAIR and standardised practices.

3.3. Section 3: Challenges and training needs in data management

Purpose

To identify the **concrete obstacles** that hinder effective, FAIR, and interoperable data management, and to determine the related **training needs** of marine and coastal citizen science initiatives.

Topics

covered

Respondents were invited to select from a predefined list of technical, organisational, and legal challenges and to indicate their training needs across various aspects of data management. Open comment fields allowed participants to describe context-specific issues or capacity gaps.

Expected

insights

This section provides a quantitative overview of the most frequent barriers encountered by MCSI, such as limited resources, insufficient expertise, or lack of guidance on FAIR implementation, and highlights where targeted capacity-building and training interventions are most urgently required.

The findings will form the evidence base for qualitative follow-up interviews in Deliverable D2.2, which will explore in greater depth the underlying causes of these challenges and refine the design of the CS-MACH1 training and support strategy.

3.4. Section 4: Engagement

Purpose

To identify priority areas for **capacity-building** and the willingness of initiatives to engage in future collaborative activities.

Topics covered

- Network participation: interest in joining our marine citizen science data network.
- Community engagement: interest in participating in joint events, being featured in newsletters, or communication activities.
- Follow-up opportunities: consent to be contacted for interviews or workshops.

Expected

insights

A summary of the level of interest and readiness among initiatives to collaborate through the marine citizen science data network, shared communication and events. The results will indicate preferred formats for engagement, identify potential partners for joint

actions, and highlight opportunities for building a **sustainable network** of marine citizen science data actors.

3.5. Closing section: Feedback and consent

Purpose

To collect feedback on the survey process and obtain consent for follow-up communication.

Topics covered

- Open comments.
- Confirmation of voluntary participation and consent for future contact.

Expected outputs

A structured summary of respondent feedback on the survey.

3.6. Analytical perspective

The modular structure of the questionnaire allows for both quantitative analysis and qualitative interpretation of open fields.

Together, these outputs form the empirical backbone of Deliverable D2.1: a factual representation of the current data management landscape in European marine citizen science.

4. Results

4.1. Section 1: General characteristics of the project

Of the **1,233 marine and coastal citizen science initiatives (MCSI)** identified, **117 projects (≈9%)** completed the survey. While not exhaustive, this sample provides a representative snapshot of the European MCSI landscape. The responses capture a broad geographic spread, with a slight bias toward Western and Northern Europe.

Overall, the surveyed initiatives reveal a **vibrant and diverse community**: most are ongoing, increasingly digital in their approach, and active across all major marine regions (from the Mediterranean and North Sea–Baltic basins to global initiatives). Common themes include biodiversity monitoring, pollution tracking, and habitat assessment, often combining volunteer-driven observations with modern technologies such as apps, GPS tools, and cameras.

The following sections present these results in greater detail, outlining the general characteristics of the participating initiatives, including their geographical scope, duration, participant composition, technological tools, and thematic focus.

4.1.1. Data-collection technologies

Survey question: “Are any technologies or tools used in the project to collect scientific data?”

(Multiple answers possible)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question, where multiple answers were possible. The results demonstrate that **digital and image-based methods dominate** marine citizen science data collection. Over four-fifths of initiatives use mobile devices and apps, selected by 98 projects (82%), reflecting the widespread adoption of app-based reporting systems that facilitate georeferenced submissions. GPS-enabled mapping (63%) and cameras are frequently used alongside these, enabling precise localisation and visual validation of observations.

Figure 1. Data-collection technologies used in marine and coastal citizen science initiatives. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of initiatives using each data-collection technology (n = 117; 390 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

A substantial proportion of projects employ sampling gear (39%) and DIY water-quality sensors (28%). The use of drones, eDNA kits, and acoustic or pattern-tracking devices highlights the diverse range of technological tools applied in citizen science operations, bridging community observation with professional oceanographic methods.

Approximately 8% of the projects reported that no specific tools were used (*NA*). A small additional share ($\approx 3\%$) relied on auxiliary materials, such as printed identification cards, litter-collection kits, or online governance-evaluation platforms, classified as “Other” due to their supporting rather than technological role in data acquisition.

Together, these findings underline the diversity, adaptability, and advancing sophistication of data-collection practices across European marine and coastal citizen science initiatives.

4.1.2. Geographical scope of the project

Survey question: “Does the project take place in a single country or a broader region?”
(Single answer)

A total of 117 initiatives responded to this question. The results show an **almost even division** between projects that operate within **national borders** and those that extend across **multiple regions**:

- Single-country initiatives: 49%
- Broader-regional or transnational initiatives: 51%

Figure 2. Geographical scope of initiatives. *Pie chart illustrating the near-equal distribution of single-country (48.7%) and broader-regional (51.3%) projects among the 117 survey respondents.*

This balanced distribution confirms that both locally anchored and multinational activities are well represented within the survey. Such diversity provides a valuable basis for later comparisons of data-handling environments operating under different regulatory and institutional frameworks.

4.1.3. Country of operation

Survey question: “In which country does the project take place?”
(Single answer)

This question was addressed to respondents who indicated in the previous item that their initiative operates within a **single national context**. A total of **57 projects** provided a valid country response.

Figure 3. Distribution of initiatives by country. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of projects per country (n = 57; single answer).*

The participating initiatives represent a wide geographical range, encompassing **23 countries** across Europe and neighbouring regions. The highest number of projects were reported from the United Kingdom, possibly reflecting a language bias due to the survey being conducted in English, followed by Spain, France, Italy, and the Netherlands. Additional representation was recorded from Portugal, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Romania, Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Croatia, Latvia, Ireland, and Malta. A limited number of contributions were also received from Tunisia, Lebanon, and Egypt reflecting collaborations extending beyond the European Union.

4.1.4. Region of operation

Survey question: “In which region does the project take place?”

(Multiple answers possible)

This question was presented to respondents who indicated that their initiative operates across a **broader region** rather than a single country. A total of **60 projects** provided valid responses. Because multiple options could be selected, the total number of regional mentions exceeds the number of projects.

Figure 4. Regional distribution of broader-region initiatives. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of broader-region projects per European or global region. (n = 60; 75 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

The responses show that **European-scale and global initiatives** are well represented in the sample. **Over one-third (43%)** of respondents indicated a **worldwide operational scope**, reflecting initiatives that collect observations across multiple ocean basins or in polar regions.

Combinations of Northern, Western, and Southern Europe were also frequently selected, showing that many projects operate across several European marine basins simultaneously. This multi-regional pattern demonstrates that interoperability challenges extend beyond national borders.

4.1.5. Marine regions

Survey question: “In which marine region does the project take place?”
(Multiple answers possible)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question, collectively reporting **288 instances of activity** across 18 marine basins, indicating that many initiatives operate in more than one region.

As shown in Figure 5, the **North Sea** was the **most frequently mentioned** area of activity (36%), followed by the North Atlantic Ocean (including the North-East Atlantic) (31%) and the Mediterranean Sea (general) (25%). Other important sub-regions included the English Channel (17%), Celtic Sea (15%), Baltic Sea (14%), and Western Mediterranean (12%). Around 22% of the total responses referred to worldwide or global ocean coverage, demonstrating the participation of European initiatives in broader ocean observation networks.

Figure 5. Distribution of initiatives across marine regions. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of initiatives reporting activity in each marine region (n = 117; 288 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

When aggregated according to the regional classification used under the **EU Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters”**: North Sea–Baltic ($\approx 65\%$), Mediterranean ($\approx 66\%$), Atlantic–Arctic ($\approx 63\%$), and Other ($\approx 27\%$), the distribution appears relatively balanced. However, the North Sea–Baltic and Mediterranean regions together account for roughly half of all reported activity, confirming these as the primary focal areas for marine citizen science in Europe.

Overall, the pattern indicates **broad geographical engagement** combined with regional concentration in Europe’s most accessible and heavily monitored marine basins. This distribution reflects both existing research infrastructure and active coastal communities that facilitate citizen science participation.

4.1.6. Project duration

Survey questions:
 “What is the start year of the project?”
 “What is the end year of the project?”
 (Single answer)

A total of 117 projects provided information on their start and end years. The start years range from before 2000 to 2025, with the median start year being 2020, indicating a marked increase in newly established initiatives during the last five years.

Approximately 80% of projects are ongoing, while 20% reported a defined end date between 2020 and 2025. The data suggest two main cohorts within the European marine and coastal citizen science landscape:

- **Established programmes (pre-2015):**
 These represent long-term monitoring initiatives, many of which began before 2010 and continue to operate, reflecting stable institutional and community engagement.
- **Recent and emerging initiatives (2018–2025):**
 This period constitutes the peak establishment phase, with more than 60% of all initiatives founded between 2018 and 2025. These projects highlight a strong expansion in marine citizen science, driven by increased digitalisation of data collection and a growing policy emphasis on citizen involvement in marine observation frameworks. This dynamic growth has been further supported by EU programmes such as Horizon 2020.

4.1.7. Participant categories

Survey question: “Who are the participants collecting the data in the project?”
 (Multiple answers possible)

Respondents were asked to identify all groups contributing to data collection within their initiatives. This question aimed to clarify the demographic and community composition of the European marine and coastal citizen science landscape.

A total of 117 projects responded, with **multiple participant types** often indicated per initiative. The vast majority of projects reported a **combination of citizen volunteers, students, and professionals** contributing to observation and sampling activities.

Figure 6. Participant types. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of projects selecting each participant category (n = 117; 329 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

The data reveal that the **wider public**, selected by 97 projects (83%), constitutes the **backbone of marine and coastal citizen science initiatives**, participating both individually and through organised associations. Students and youth groups (55%) form the second-largest category, underscoring the strong educational dimension of marine citizen science. Specialised participant types such as divers (36%), water-sports enthusiasts (32%), and fishermen (29%) play essential roles in underwater and nearshore monitoring, providing observations that would otherwise be logistically or financially difficult to obtain through institutional programmes.

A smaller yet important share of projects involve professional or institutional actors, such as scientists, staff of a non-governmental organization (NGO), rangers of a marine protected area (MPA), nature guides, and coastal professionals, who support data validation, coordination, and capacity building. This “other participants” (13%) group also includes skilled volunteers and citizen experts (e.g. benthic samplers and amateur naturalists), as well as initiatives engaging social inclusion groups such as persons with disabilities and migrants through participatory frameworks.

Their involvement demonstrates that marine citizen science extends well beyond public volunteering, operating as a multi-stakeholder collaboration that bridges citizens, professionals, and organised civil-society actors. Such diversity contributes not only to the credibility and continuity of data collection but also to the social inclusiveness of the broader marine observation ecosystem.

4.1.8. Scale of participation

Survey question: “What is the approximate number of participants per year?”
(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question, revealing wide variation in the size of participating communities. As shown in Figure 7, participation levels range from small to large-scale programmes.

Figure 7. Approximate number of participants per year. *Pie chart showing the percentage of initiatives by annual number of active participants (n = 117; single answer).*

Roughly one-fifth of initiatives (21%) reported having more than 1,000 participants per year, indicating the presence of large, well-established citizen science networks. An equal share (21%) reported 11–50 participants, while 22% involved 101–500 contributors annually. About 16% of projects counted 51–100 active participants, and 13% reached between 501 and 1,000 participants. Only a small fraction (8%) represented very small initiatives with fewer than a dozen volunteers.

Overall, these figures point to a broadly balanced distribution of project sizes rather than a clear bimodal pattern. The majority of initiatives ($\approx 60\%$) involve between 11 and 500 participants, forming a strong middle tier of medium-sized efforts that combine community involvement with organised data collection.

4.1.9. Frequency of activities or events

Survey question: “What is the frequency of the activity or event?”
(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects provided responses, revealing diverse temporal patterns in how citizen science activities are organised and implemented across marine and coastal initiatives.

Figure 8. Frequency of activities and events. *Pie chart illustrating the proportion of initiatives by frequency of activity (n = 117; single answer).*

The **majority** of initiatives operate either on a **continuous basis (39%)** or with irregular activity patterns (21%), reflecting the highly flexible nature of marine citizen science engagement.

Roughly one-third of projects follow seasonal, annual, or monthly schedules, typically corresponding to biological or environmental monitoring cycles (e.g. breeding

seasons, beach-litter campaigns, phytoplankton sampling). Shorter-term initiatives, such as one-day or weekly events, account for only a small proportion (3%).

4.1.10. Main topics of the projects

Survey question: “What is the main topic of the project?”

(Multiple answers possible)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. Because many initiatives address several aspects of the marine environment simultaneously, respondents were allowed to select multiple thematic areas. The response categories were developed in alignment with the **Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)** defined by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), ensuring consistency with internationally recognised observation frameworks.

Figure 9. Main project topics. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of initiatives addressing each main topic (n = 117; 257 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

The results reveal that **marine biodiversity, pollution, and habitat monitoring dominate**

the European marine and coastal citizen science landscape, complemented by contributions to physical and chemical ocean observation.

The analysis highlights that biodiversity observations and species monitoring, selected by 78 projects (67%), remains the cornerstone of marine and coastal citizen science in Europe, with two-thirds of all initiatives involved in species identification, population monitoring, or habitat assessment. The strong representation of marine pollution-related projects (46%) underscores the prominence of public engagement in tackling marine litter and chemical contamination, topics that resonate widely with citizens and policy makers alike.

Physical and chemical ocean parameters such as temperature (15%), oxygen (6%), and nutrients (5%) are also monitored by a smaller but significant subset of projects. Finally, a limited number of projects focus on climate and atmospheric processes, such as greenhouse gases and weather observations, or on socio-economic and governance dimensions, reflecting the diversity of approaches within the European marine citizen science landscape.

4.2. Section 2: Data flow

This section examines how marine and coastal citizen science initiatives currently **manage, store, and disseminate their data**. The results show a community that increasingly recognises the importance of sound data stewardship and is gradually adopting more structured and interoperable practices, while notable variability persists among projects.

Overall, most initiatives report a solid foundation in data management, with a considerable proportion already applying elements of the FAIR principles and standardised methodologies. The widespread use of **cloud-based and hybrid storage** solutions reflects an emerging emphasis on **accessibility, collaboration, and scalability**. At the same time, a significant share of projects continues to rely on locally managed or institution-specific storage systems, which poses ongoing challenges for long-term preservation and interoperability.

Progress towards **data standardisation** is also evident. Many initiatives have begun to harmonise their datasets and metadata in accordance with recognised marine and biodiversity data frameworks, such as **EMODnet, GBIF, and EurOBIS**. Nevertheless, disparities remain in the extent of metadata documentation, the openness of data publication practices, and the formal recognition of citizen contributions.

In summary, the current dataflow landscape of European marine and coastal citizen science is characterised by both advancement due to the increased value of citizens collecting data and the use of growing technologies like smartphones and AI and

heterogeneity because of varied data quality, challenges in standardizing data and ensuring clear policies for data exist.

4.2.1. Experience with data management

Survey question: “Do you have experience in managing data?”
(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. The results indicate that the majority of marine and coastal citizen science initiatives have a relatively high level of data management experience.

The data show that over two-thirds (**68%**) of initiatives have **direct experience** in managing datasets, suggesting that citizen science practitioners are not merely data collectors but also engage in aspects of curation, storage, and sharing. Another **30%** report having **partial experience**.

Only a very small number (**≈2%**) indicated having **no experience**. Overall, the responses reflect a maturing citizen science landscape in which community-led projects are increasingly aware of the technical and organisational demands of responsible data stewardship.

Figure 10. Experience with data management. *Pie chart showing the proportion of initiatives reporting experience in data management (n = 117; single answer).*

4.2.2. Data storage

Survey question: “Where is the project data stored?”
 (Multiple answers possible; responses normalised to 100%)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. Because multiple answers were possible, respondents could indicate more than one storage environment. To help interpret the results, the three storage categories are defined as follows:

- **Local storage:** data saved directly on personal devices, such as laptops, desktops, smartphones, or external hard drives used by project contributors.
- **Internal storage:** storage environments provided and managed by the institution running the project (e.g. institutional servers, on-premise systems, internal network drives).
- **External storage:** systems hosted outside the institution, such as commercial cloud services (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox), third-party repositories, or platforms managed by external partners.

The results are presented in two complementary ways:

1. The **pie chart** shows the normalised percentages of all storage configurations, summing to 100%, and thus representing the *relative distribution* of how different storage types and combinations are used across projects.
2. The **bar chart** shows the *absolute number of selections* for each storage category, independent of combinations between options.

Figure 11. Storage environments used for citizen science data (normalised to 100%). *Pie chart showing the relative distribution of storage configurations among projects (117 respondents; multiple answers possible; normalised to 100%).*

The results indicate a **heterogeneous landscape of data storage practices** among marine and coastal citizen science initiatives. No single environment is dominant. The most frequent configuration is external/cloud-only storage (27%), followed by internal institutional servers (21%) and combined internal–external systems (22%). Other mixed arrangements include local + internal + external (13%), local + external (9%), and local + internal (3%), while only 5% of projects rely exclusively on local storage.

Figure 12. Storage environments used for citizen science data (total selections). *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of initiatives using each type of storage environment (n = 117; 187 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

When looking at the total counts, external storage was selected 83 times, internal storage 69 times, and local storage 35 times. This highlights that external or cloud-based systems are the most prevalent overall, but many projects still combine them with institutional or local solutions.

4.2.3. Standardisation of data and metadata

Survey question: “At this moment, the data of the project are raw, converted or partially converted?”

(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. The results indicate a heterogeneous level of progress in standardising citizen science data and metadata.

As shown in Figure 13, **39%** of initiatives report that their data are already **converted** into a consistent, standard format. Another **33%** indicate that their data are **partially converted**, suggesting that harmonisation efforts are underway but not yet complete.

Figure 13. Standardisation status of citizen science data. *Pie chart showing the proportion of initiatives reporting their current data standardisation level (n = 117; single answer).*

These findings show that while a majority of projects (over 70%) have made at least partial progress towards standardisation, a substantial portion still manage non-harmonised or raw data, limiting interoperability with other datasets and infrastructures. The 10% of respondents who were uncertain about their standardisation status likely represent projects without dedicated data management expertise or formalised metadata documentation.

Overall, these results underscore the need for **targeted training and guidance** on data-standardisation workflows and the use of recognised marine data vocabularies to align citizen science outputs with FAIR principles and existing marine data systems.

4.2.4. FAIR awareness

Survey question: “Have you ever heard of the FAIR principles for data management?”

(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. The results show that most initiatives are at least familiar with the FAIR principles and actively attempt to apply them.

Figure 14. Awareness and application of FAIR principles. *Pie chart showing the proportion of initiatives reporting awareness and application of the FAIR principles (n = 117; single answer).*

The data reveal a **strong awareness** of the **FAIR framework (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)** across European marine and coastal citizen science initiatives. Nearly two-thirds of respondents (62%) actively strive to implement FAIR principles, reflecting a growing culture of responsible and open data management within the community. An additional 20% are aware of FAIR but have not yet adopted the approach—often citing limited technical capacity, infrastructure access, or uncertainty about how to operationalise FAIR in small-scale projects.

Only 17% of projects reported no familiarity with FAIR principles, highlighting a clear opportunity for capacity building and training. These results emphasise that, while awareness is high, implementation remains uneven and would benefit from targeted guidance on metadata standards, repository integration, and open-data workflows.

4.2.5. Use of best practices and standardised protocols

Survey question: “Does the project currently use or document any best practices, standardised methods, protocols, tools, or guidelines for citizen science data collection, management, or sharing?”

(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. Nearly **seven out of ten initiatives (69%)** reported **using or documenting best practices, protocols, or standardised methods**, indicating a widespread awareness of the importance of methodological consistency and data reliability in citizen science workflows. These practices encompass a wide range of approaches, from defined sampling methodologies and structured data-submission formats to alignment with recognised marine observation frameworks.

Figure 15. Use of best practices and standardised protocols. *Pie chart showing the proportion of initiatives using or documenting best practices, standardised methods, or protocols (n = 117; single answer).*

Among those that provided further detail, many cited the **use of international standards**, such as the Darwin Core format and the FAIR principles, and integration in bigger data infrastructures (GBIF, EurOBIS, EMODnet). Others adhere to formal guidelines such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), OSPAR protocols, and the Joint Cetacean Data Protocol (JCDP), demonstrating that citizen science data are increasingly compatible with professional marine and biodiversity monitoring systems.

Several respondents described the use of custom-developed protocols and tools, such as iNaturalist, MINKA, or bespoke mobile applications featuring fixed geographic zones, photographic validation, and expert review. Others reported structured training materials, species-identification cards, and video tutorials designed to ensure consistent data collection by volunteers.

In addition, a number of projects highlighted national or thematic frameworks, including Plastic Pirates, Artportalen, TurtleWatch Egypt, and Plages Vivantes, which each provide tailored guidelines for their participant communities. Some respondents also shared links to published protocols and datasets on Zenodo, GitHub, or in peer-reviewed journals, underscoring their commitment to open and reproducible science.

Conversely, around 31% of respondents indicated that they do not yet apply such frameworks. This finding underscores the continued need for shared templates, training materials, and harmonised guidance to ensure that data collected through diverse citizen science efforts can be aggregated and compared effectively across Europe.

Overall, the responses illustrate that methodological standardisation is already well embedded in a large share of marine and coastal citizen science initiatives, but that there remains scope for greater interoperability and capacity-building to consolidate these advances across the broader community.

4.2.6. Data findability

Survey question: “Is the project data findable at this moment?”

(Single answer)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. Slightly more than half (**56%**) indicated that their data are currently **findable**, while 44% reported that their datasets are not yet discoverable through public or institutional channels.

Figure 16. Data findability. *Pie chart showing the proportion of initiatives reporting whether their project data are currently findable (n = 117; single answer).*

Among the initiatives confirming data findability, the qualitative answers reveal a wide variety of publication environments and visibility mechanisms. Many projects host their datasets on **institutional websites, thematic data portals, or open repositories** such as GBIF, [Zenodo](#), EMODnet, EurOBIS, and [PANGAEA](#). Several others make data accessible through project-specific dashboards or interactive mapping interfaces (e.g. *MarineInfo*, *MINKA*, *Happywhale*, *Eye on Water*, *The Ocean Movement Dashboard*), providing users with visual insights or download options for observation data.

A number of initiatives rely on **national or regional biodiversity databases**, including Artportalen (Sweden), iRecord and NBN Atlas (UK), or the National Biodiversity Data Centre (Ireland), which facilitate data discovery through structured metadata and Darwin Core-compliant records. In other cases, data is integrated into citizen science platforms such as *iNaturalist* or *Observation.org*, ensuring both visibility and standardisation across projects.

Several respondents highlighted that their datasets are findable but with controlled or **partial access**, particularly where sensitive species information or privacy considerations apply. Some projects therefore use metadata truncation, coordinate rounding, or request-based download systems to balance transparency with data protection. Others reported ongoing transitions, such as migrating data to EMODnet, GBIF, or institutional servers, to strengthen findability and interoperability in the near future.

Conversely, the remaining 44% of initiatives reported that their data are not yet discoverable, often because they are in an early developmental phase or rely on internal storage without metadata publication. This gap underscores that, while awareness of the FAIR data principles is relatively high, the “Findable” component remains only partially implemented across the marine and coastal citizen science landscape. To address this, future capacity-building efforts should prioritise training in data-publication workflows, including metadata creation, assignment of persistent identifiers (DOIs), and linking to established open-data infrastructures.

4.2.7. Data accessibility

Survey question: “The data of the project are accessible by...”

(Multiple answers possible; responses normalised to 100%)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. The vast majority (**73%**) of initiatives make their data **accessible for everyone**, reflecting a strong alignment with open-data principles within the marine and coastal citizen science community. Smaller shares of projects limit access to project partners (11%), their own institute (7%), or both the institute and project partners (7%). Only 2% of projects indicated that their data are accessible only to themselves.

Figure 17. Data accessibility. Pie chart showing the relative share of data accessibility levels among projects (n = 117; multiple answers possible; normalised to 100%).

These results show a clear tendency toward openness and public accessibility. Most initiatives embrace transparency and shared access to support collaboration and reuse of citizen science data. However, the presence of restricted and institution-based access in a subset of projects suggests that organisational policies, technical limitations, or ethical considerations still influence data-sharing practices within the community.

4.2.8. Data publication platforms

Survey question: “If the data of the project are already (publicly) accessible, on which platforms are they available?”

(Multiple answers possible)

A total of 117 projects responded: 14% of respondents this question is not (yet) applicable for their project, meaning their data are not yet publicly accessible. This highlights the **transitional stage of data stewardship** within the MCSI community, where many projects are progressing from internal data storage toward open dissemination. When a project dedicated website exists 41% of initiatives already make their data available. However, the data sharing practices do not always align with the FAIR principles in these cases. Some examples are lack of metadata or even non existing, unclear access protocols, not interoperable formats, lack of domain-specific standards and missing or unclear licenses.

Figure 18. Publication platforms used by projects. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of initiatives addressing each platform (n = 117; 156 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

The number of citizen-science tools, collaborative platforms and mobile apps facilitates data collection by citizen scientists. A total of 50 respondents (43%) currently use apps or platforms that are dedicated to, or designed for, specific projects or domains (environmental science, biodiversity, public and social sciences). The apps specifically used to monitor the marine and coastal environment are:

- The Shark Trust, Whale Track, Sea Watcher: observations on marine megafauna
- CoastSnap: monitoring changes to coastlines
- Sea Angling Diary: logging of fishing activities and catches for sustainable management of fish stocks
- Mini Secchi, Secchi, EyeonWater colour: observations on water clarity and colour temperature
- Beach Explorer, Marnoba, EAA Marine LitterWatch, The Ocean Cleanup Survey: observations on marine litter pollution
- Fish & Click: observations of lost or abandoned fishing gear

Next to specific marine apps, citizen science projects frequently use global biodiversity citizen science data platforms such as iNaturalist, Observation.org, iRecord and iSPOT. All research grade observations from these platforms are published in GBIF.

Notable fractions (5%) reference the MINKA Citizen Science Observatory as their marine data platform. MINKA is a platform acting as a participatory citizen science observatory on biodiversity data. 23% of projects generally store data in their **national databases** which are made available in **national data portals**.

Looking into publishing biodiversity data in (marine) international data portals and databases, the most frequently mentioned are GBIF (20%), EMODnet (14%) and (Eur)OBIS (7%) underscoring their importance as key nodes for the integration of European marine and coastal citizen science data. Next to these Zenodo and [Figshare](#) are used as general data repositories. Also, PANGAEA and [SEANOE](#) are used as international oceanographic data portals for storing and sharing datasets. This shows

that citizen science data are increasingly connected to established marine and biodiversity data networks.

Last, 3% of projects contribute to EU initiatives (EU Copernicus Marine Service and EU Atlas of the Seas) which provide data about the marine environment.

4.2.9. Tracking and recognition of citizen contributions

Survey question: “Does the project use any form of tracking or recognition to give credit to participating citizens?”

(Multiple answers possible; responses normalised to 100%)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question. Respondents could select more than one option, as some initiatives apply both formal and informal recognition practices. To ensure comparability, results were normalised to 100%, showing the relative share of each recognition type.

Figure 19. Tracking and recognition of citizen contribution. *Horizontal bar chart showing the proportion of initiatives applying different recognition mechanisms (117 respondents; multiple answers possible; normalised to 100 %).*

The results reveal that the majority of marine and coastal citizen science initiatives (91%) implement some form of credit or recognition for participants. **Informal recognition** dominates, applied by **around 55%** of projects, typically through thank-you messages, community acknowledgements, or public appreciation via social media or newsletters. **Formal recognition** mechanisms are used by **36%** of initiatives, for instance through authorship, certificates, acknowledgements in publications, or digital tracking systems.

A smaller share of projects (9%) report **no formalised recognition system**, often citing anonymisation requirements, privacy regulations, or limited administrative capacity as reasons.

Overall, these findings indicate that recognition of citizen contributions is a widespread but heterogeneous practice within European marine and coastal citizen science. While structured credit systems remain less common, the strong prevalence of informal recognition reflects the social and motivational importance of acknowledging volunteers’ efforts and fostering long-term engagement.

4.3. Section 3: Challenges and training needs in data management

This section explores the main obstacles and capacity gaps encountered by marine and coastal citizen science initiatives (MCSI) in handling their data. Respondents were invited to identify both the challenges that hinder effective, FAIR, and interoperable data management, and the training needs required to overcome these barriers. Together, these results provide a diagnostic overview of the community’s current limitations and priorities for capacity-building, serving as a foundation for the targeted actions foreseen in WP2 Deliverable 2.2.

4.3.1. Major challenges in data management

Survey question: “What are currently the project’s major challenges in terms of data management?”

(Multiple answers)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question, identifying a wide range of obstacles that affect how MSCI manage their data.

Figure 20. Major challenges in data management. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of projects identifying specific challenges in data management (n = 117 respondents; 309 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

By far the most frequently reported barrier is **lack of funds**, cited by **71 projects (61%)**. This confirms that financial constraints remain the single most significant obstacle to sustaining data workflows, from collection to publication. **Limited time availability**, mentioned by **51 respondents (44%)**, follows closely, reflecting the dependence of many initiatives on volunteers or part-time staff who struggle to maintain regular data-management routines.

Other common issues include data-quality and consistency problems (27%), interoperability challenges with external systems (22%), and technical barriers such as insufficient storage or inadequate tools (16%). Together, these highlight the **need for stronger technical infrastructure** and clearer methodological guidance.

Human-capacity constraints are also evident: limited institutional support (20.5 %), lack of data-science expertise (19%), and insufficient training (5%) point to gaps in available skills and support mechanisms. Legal or ethical concerns (11%), including data protection (GDPR) and licensing, were also mentioned by several respondents.

A small number of initiatives noted no major challenges (4%), while unclear roles or responsibilities (3%) were least frequently reported. Overall, these results depict a landscape where financial, temporal, and technical limitations continue to hinder progress toward robust and FAIR-aligned data stewardship. Addressing these barriers will require not only targeted funding but also sustained investment in skills development, interoperability, and institutional support.

4.3.2. Training needs in data management

Survey question: “What are the project training needs in terms of data management?” (Multiple answers possible)

A total of 117 projects responded to this question, identifying clear areas where further training is needed to strengthen data-related workflows within MCSI.

Figure 21. Training needs in data management. *Horizontal bar chart showing the number of projects identifying specific training needs in data management (n = 117; 316 total selections; multiple answers possible).*

The most frequently expressed need concerns **data analysis and visualisation**, selected by **57 projects (49%)**, indicating strong demand for capacity building in transforming raw citizen science data into interpretable and policy-relevant insights. **Data quality assurance (43%)** and **use of technology and tools (41%)** follow closely, underlining the importance of ensuring methodological rigour and technological proficiency across initiatives.

Further training needs are identified in communication and outreach (37%) and data management and storage (33%), reflecting ongoing efforts to professionalise data stewardship and enhance interoperability between systems. Use of digital platforms or apps for sharing data (27%) also features prominently, illustrating the increasing focus on open data and online dissemination practices.

More specific topics, such as legal and ethical aspects (19%) and project coordination and planning (19%), are less frequently cited but remain relevant, particularly for initiatives dealing with cross-border collaboration or sensitive information. Only 3 initiatives (3%) reported no current training needs, suggesting that nearly all respondents recognise the value of further skill development in one or more areas of data management.

Overall, the findings confirm a community-wide call for practical, hands-on training, especially in data processing, quality control, and digital tool usage, complemented by growing attention to communication and ethical data handling within the European marine and coastal citizen science landscape.

4.4. Section 4: Engagement

A total of 117 projects responded to the questions on engagement and willingness to collaborate within the marine and coastal citizen science community.

The results reveal **a remarkably high level of interest in networked collaboration and communication** across the surveyed initiatives. An overwhelming 93% of respondents expressed interest in joining an informal marine citizen science data network, while 92% indicated they would like to participate in joint online or physical events with other project coordinators, data managers, and technology developers. Similarly, over 90% of projects wish to receive the CS-MACH1 newsletter, and 87% are open to having their project featured through CS-MACH1's communication channels.

When asked about future collaboration and follow-up, 69% of respondents agreed to take part in a one-hour follow-up interview, showing a strong willingness to contribute more in-depth insights. Among those using sensors or other data-collection technologies, 54% consented to being contacted for more technical discussions, while 43% marked this as not applicable to their work.

These findings collectively demonstrate broad enthusiasm for cooperation, visibility, and knowledge exchange within the European marine citizen science community. They provide a solid foundation for establishing a community of practice under WP2, supporting sustained dialogue, capacity building, and coordinated data management improvement across initiatives.

4.5. Closing section: Feedback and consent

The closing section invited participants to share open feedback, suggestions, or further comments on the survey and its broader objectives. Responses reveal a high degree of engagement and constructive reflection among the participating initiatives.

Several respondents **expressed appreciation** for the initiative, describing it as timely, relevant, and valuable for strengthening collaboration within the marine citizen science community. Many projects indicated a strong willingness to stay informed about upcoming developments, to participate in future activities, or to contribute to the emerging network.

Feedback also pointed to **practical and structural challenges** faced by initiatives. Respondents highlighted persistent limitations in **funding, time, and personnel**, as well as specific needs for **communication and outreach support**, particularly to engage broader audiences such as tourists and local communities. Others noted technical and organisational barriers, such as maintaining data quality, ensuring interoperability, and finding sustainable hosting or data management solutions suited to citizen science contexts.

Several contributions offered thoughtful suggestions for the future direction of the CS-MACH1 network. These included calls for more thematic focus areas (e.g. marine biodiversity or marine litter), translation of key materials, and dedicated capacity-

building efforts tailored to varying levels of expertise. Some respondents shared detailed project experiences or ongoing innovations, from school-based monitoring systems to sophisticated cloud-based architectures, underscoring the diversity and creativity within the community.

Finally, multiple projects expressed explicit interest in future collaboration, joint funding applications, and knowledge exchange under the CS-MACH1 umbrella. Collectively, this feedback confirms both the enthusiasm and the readiness of the European marine citizen science community to move toward greater coordination, mutual support, and shared learning in the coming phases of WP2.

5. Discussion and outlook

This preliminary assessment provides a consolidated picture of a **diverse yet maturing** European marine and coastal citizen science landscape. Projects increasingly employ **digital and image-based tools**, such as mobile applications, GPS, and online reporting systems, to collect data. They store information across **hybrid environments**, combining local, institutional, and cloud-based systems. Awareness of the **FAIR data principles** is widespread, though their practical implementation, especially regarding findability, metadata completeness, and data publication, remains uneven. Most initiatives report partial or full progress toward data standardisation, and open accessibility is becoming a defining feature, even as long-term stewardship and systematic workflows still vary widely.

At the same time, the survey reveals **strong foundations** within the community. Many initiatives already connect to established infrastructures such as **EMODnet**, **GBIF**, **EurOBIS**, and **Zenodo**, illustrating that citizen science data is gradually integrating into the broader European marine data ecosystem. Recognition of citizen contributions is also widespread, often through informal means (thank-you messages, community visibility) and, in a smaller but growing number of cases, through formal credit systems such as authorship, certificates, or acknowledgements. The wide range of participant types (citizens, students, divers, professionals, and educators) underscores the social inclusiveness and interdisciplinary strength of marine and coastal citizen science.

However, several **persistent challenges** remain. Limited funding and time availability continue to be the most significant obstacles for good and robust data management, followed by issues related to data quality, interoperability, and insufficient technical or analytical capacity. Although awareness of FAIR principles is high, many initiatives still struggle with **metadata quality, persistent identifiers, and licensing**, constraining data reusability. The coexistence of

multiple storage modes further complicates version control, traceability, and long-term preservation.

These insights will directly inform the **next phase of D2.1 of WP2**, which will adopt a qualitative approach through 10 interviews.

6. Annexes

6.1. Annex 1: survey questionnaire

The following annex contains the full set of questions used in the CS-MACH1 Survey.

CS-MACH1 survey: help shape the future of marine citizen science data!

* Indicates required question

This survey is part of the [CS-MACH1 project](#), funded by the EU Horizon Europe programme. The project aims to strengthen the **marine citizen science data community** and improve how data is collected, managed, and shared across Europe and beyond.

With this questionnaire we want to learn how marine/coastal citizen science projects are currently handling their data – from collection to storage and sharing – and where additional support or training could be useful.

Completing the survey will take about **15–20 minutes**. If you coordinate more than one project, please fill in a separate form for each. This survey is intended for projects collecting data in the **marine or marine–riverine environment** (no other purely freshwater bodies).

Your responses will be processed in line with the **EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**. All personal data will be treated confidentially, used only for project purposes, and stored securely. Participation is voluntary, and you may access, correct, or request deletion of your data at any time. For questions, please contact csmach1@vliz.be.

Thank you in advance for your time and valuable contribution!

IDENTIFICATION OF THE PROJECT AND COORDINATING PERSON

1. What is the name of the project? *

2. What is the name (first name and last name) of the main coordinator? *

3. What is the email address of the main coordinator?

4. What is the URL of the project's website? *

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROJECT

5. Are any technologies or tools used in the project to collect scientific data? If yes, please select all that apply from the list below. *

Tick all that apply.

- Mobile devices and apps
- GPS and mapping tools
- Drones and remotely operated vehicles
- Cameras and imaging equipment
- Water quality sensors and DIY kits measuring physico-chemical water parameters
- Sampling gear
- Acoustic tools
- Pattern tracking devices (e.g., currents, waves, sea level)
- Biodiversity & species monitoring kits (e.g., eDNA)
- NA (not applicable for the project)
- Other: _____

6. Does the project take place in a single country or a broader region? *

If the project takes place in a single country (e.g., only in Belgium), select 'single country'. If you coordinate a project that covers more countries or a broader region (e.g., Western Europe, Eastern Europe), please select 'broader region'.

Mark only one oval.

- Single country *Skip to question 7*
- Broader region *Skip to question 8*

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROJECT

7. In which country does the project take place? *

Mark only one oval.

- Albania *Skip to question 9*
- Algeria *Skip to question 9*
- Andorra *Skip to question 9*
- Armenia *Skip to question 9*
- Austria *Skip to question 9*
- Azerbaijan *Skip to question 9*
- Belarus *Skip to question 9*
- Belgium *Skip to question 9*
- Bosnia and Herzegovina *Skip to question 9*
- Bulgaria *Skip to question 9*
- Croatia *Skip to question 9*
- Cyprus *Skip to question 9*
- Czech Republic *Skip to question 9*
- Denmark *Skip to question 9*
- Egypt *Skip to question 9*
- Estonia *Skip to question 9*
- Finland *Skip to question 9*
- France *Skip to question 9*
- Georgia *Skip to question 9*
- Germany *Skip to question 9*
- Greece *Skip to question 9*
- Hungary *Skip to question 9*
- Iceland *Skip to question 9*
- Iran *Skip to question 9*
- Ireland *Skip to question 9*
- Italy *Skip to question 9*
- Kazakhstan *Skip to question 9*
- Kosovo *Skip to question 9*
- Latvia *Skip to question 9*
- Lebanon *Skip to question 9*
- Liechtenstein *Skip to question 9*
- Lithuania *Skip to question 9*
- Luxembourg *Skip to question 9*
- Malta *Skip to question 9*
- Moldova *Skip to question 9*
- Monaco *Skip to question 9*
- Montenegro *Skip to question 9*
- Morocco *Skip to question 9*
- Netherlands *Skip to question 9*
- North Macedonia *Skip to question 9*
- Norway *Skip to question 9*
- Poland *Skip to question 9*
- Portugal *Skip to question 9*
- Romania *Skip to question 9*

- Russia *Skip to question 9*
- San Marino *Skip to question 9*
- Serbia *Skip to question 9*
- Slovakia *Skip to question 9*
- Slovenia *Skip to question 9*
- Spain *Skip to question 9*
- Sweden *Skip to question 9*
- Switzerland *Skip to question 9*
- Syria *Skip to question 9*
- Tunisia *Skip to question 9*
- Turkey *Skip to question 9*
- Ukraine *Skip to question 9*
- United Kingdom *Skip to question 9*
- Other: _____

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROJECT

8. In which region does the project take place? *

Tick all that apply.

- Baltic States (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania)
- Eastern Europe (Poland, Czechia, Slovakia, Hungary, Ukraine, Belarus, Moldova, Russia)
- Northern Europe (Nordic countries: Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden)
- South-Eastern Europe (Balkans: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Bulgaria, Romania, Greece, Slovenia, Kosovo)
- Southern Europe (Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Malta)
- Western Europe (France, Germany, Belgium, Netherlands, Luxembourg, Switzerland, Austria)
- Worldwide
- Other: _____

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROJECT

9. In which marine region does the project take place? *

Tick all that apply.

- It's a river-based project
- Adriatic Sea
- Aegean Sea
- Baltic Sea
- Barents Sea
- Bay of Biscay
- Black Sea
- Celtic Sea
- Central Mediterranean Sea
- Eastern Mediterranean Sea
- English Channel
- Greenland Sea
- Ionian Sea
- Ligurian Sea
- Mediterranean Sea (general)
- North Atlantic Ocean
- North Sea
- Norwegian Sea
- Skagerrak & Kattegat
- Tyrrhenian Sea
- Western Mediterranean Sea
- White Sea
- Other: _____

10. What is the start year of the project? *

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- 2025
- 2024
- 2023
- 2022
- 2021
- 2020
- 2019
- 2018
- 2017
- 2016
- 2015
- 2014
- 2013
- 2012
- 2011
- 2010
- 2009
- 2008
- 2007
- 2006
- 2005
- 2004
- 2003
- 2002
- 2001
- 2000
- Before 2000

11. What is the end year of the project? *

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- The project is ongoing
- 2025
- 2024
- 2023
- 2022
- 2021
- 2020
- 2019
- 2018
- 2017
- 2016
- 2015
- 2014
- 2013
- 2012
- 2011
- 2010
- 2009
- 2008
- 2007
- 2006
- 2005
- 2004
- 2003
- 2002
- 2001
- 2000
- Before 2000

12. Who are the participants collecting the data in the project? *

Tick all that apply.

- Wider public
- Water sports enthusiasts / marinas
- Divers
- Beach guards
- Fishermen
- Students and/or youth groups
- Tourists
- Other: _____

13. What is the approximate number of participants per year? *

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- 1–11
- 11–50
- 51–100
- 101–500
- 501–1,000
- 1,000+

14. What is the frequency of the activity or event? *

Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- One-day event
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Quarterly
- Seasonal
- Annually
- Continuous
- Irregular

15. What is the main topic of the project? *

Tick all that apply.

- Currents
- Salinity
- Sea level
- Sea state
- Ocean Surface Heat Flux
- Water temperature
- Ocean color / plankton / harmful algal blooms
- Oxygen
- Nutrients
- Green house gases
- Marine habitats
- Biodiversity observations and/or species monitoring (e.g., fish, birds, mammals, ...)
- DNA-derived biological occurrences (DNA from individual organisms, but also from environmental DNA)
- Marine pollution (chemicals, plastics, ...)
- Coastal erosion
- Fisheries / sustainable fishing
- Weather observations
- Noise pollution
- Other: _____

DATA-FLOW NOW

16. Citizen science is hot! All over the world we are collecting all types of data. *
Do you have experience in managing data?

⌵ Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 Partially
 No

17. Where is the project data stored? *

Tick all that apply.

- Locally (e.g., PC, laptop, external drive, USB)
 Internal institutional storage (e.g., shared network drives, institutional servers)
 External/cloud storage (e.g., Google Drive, Dropbox, OneDrive, SharePoint)
 Other: _____

18. Standardization of data and metadata makes information understandable, interoperable, and readily exchangeable with other datasets. It refers to the process of converting raw (meta)data into a consistent, standard format. *

At this moment, the data of the project are:

Mark only one oval.

- Raw
 Converted
 Partially converted
 I don't know

19. Have you ever heard of the FAIR principles for data management? *

The FAIR principles are international guidelines for research data management that aim to maximize the reuse of research data. FAIR data are data that are **F**indable (**F**), **A**ccessible (**A**), **I**nteroperable (**I**), and **R**eusable (**R**).

Mark only one oval.

- No
 Yes, but my project does not use the FAIR principles
 Yes, my project tries to use the FAIR principles
 Other: _____

20. Does the project currently use or document any best practices, standardized methods, protocols, tools or guidelines for citizen science data collection, management, or sharing? *

E.g., standardized protocols for water quality measurements, guidelines for recording species observations, metadata templates for marine data, tools for managing coastal monitoring results, or policies for sharing datasets according to FAIR principles.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes Skip to question 21
 No Skip to question 22

21. You answered 'yes' to the question: *Does the project currently use or document any best practices, standardized methods, protocols, tools, or guidelines for citizen science data collection, management, or sharing?* Please specify or provide links if available: *

22. Is the project data findable at this moment? *

Data is discoverable via search engines and catalogues with the help of a rich set of metadata allowing its discovery. Metadata are always openly accessible, even if the data are restricted or under embargo.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes Skip to question 23
- No Skip to question 24

23. You answered 'yes' to the question: *Is the project data findable at this moment?* Please specify or provide links if available: *

DATA-FLOW NOW

24. The data of the project are accessible by: *

Tick all that apply.

- Only me
- My institute
- Project partners
- Accessible for everyone
- Other: _____

25. If the data of the project are already (publicly) accessible, on which platforms are they available? *

Tick all that apply.

- Dropbox
- (Eur)OBIS
- EDITO
- EMODnet
- GBIF
- Google Drive
- ICES
- OneDrive
- PANGAEA
- SeaDataNet
- SharePoint
- Zenodo
- NA (not applicable for the project)
- Other: _____

26. Does the project use any form of tracking or recognition to give credit to participating citizens? *

Tick all that apply.

- Yes, formally (e.g., authorship, digital badges, acknowledgments)
- Yes, informally (e.g., thank-you messages, community recognition)
- No, we do not track or recognize contributions
- Other: _____

CHALLENGES AND NEEDS WITH REGARDS TO DATA MANAGEMENT

27. What are currently the project major challenges in terms of data management? *

Tick all that apply.

- Dirty data
- No time
- Unavailability or difficult access to data
- Lack of own knowledge
- Lack of guidelines
- Lack of funds to do the work
- Limited support in the project
- Lack of data science talent or experts in the project
- No training
- Unclear responsibilities or roles within the project
- Technical barriers (e.g., storage, tools)
- Data quality or consistency issues
- Legal or ethical concerns (e.g., privacy, licensing)
- Interoperability with (integration in) other data systems or platforms
- Other: _____

28. What are the project training needs in terms of data management? *

Tick all that apply.

- Data collection methods
- Data quality assurance
- Data management and storage
- Use of technology and tools
- Data analysis and visualization
- Use of digital platforms or apps for sharing data
- Communication and outreach
- Legal and ethical aspects (e.g., GDPR, licensing)
- Project coordination and planning
- Other: _____

CITIZEN SCIENCE DATA NETWORK

29. Are you interested in being part of an informal citizen science data network? *

CS-MACH1 aims to establish a long-lasting network of stakeholders to enhance the use of marine citizen science data for societal benefit. The network seeks to connect (1) marine citizen science project coordinators, (2) low-cost technology developers, (3) data managers, and (4) potential users of the data (scientists and policy makers). As a coordinator of a marine citizen science project, are you interested in joining the network? You should be part of it!

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

30. Are you interested in participating in a joint physical or online event with other marine/coastal citizen science project coordinators, data managers, designers of low-cost technology, and potential users of your data? *

The workshop will take place on February 3 and 4, 2026, in Ostend. Please note: this does not count as a registration, but merely indicates your interest.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

31. Would you like your marine or coastal citizen science project to be considered for featuring in the CS-MACH1 communication channels (newsletter, social media, etc.)? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

32. Are you interested in receiving the CS-MACH1 newsletter? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

33. If your project uses sensors/technologies/tools, may we contact you for more detailed information about this aspect? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Not applicable

34. Would you be open to discussing your answers in a one-hour (maximum) follow-up interview? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 Preferably not

LAST PART!

35. Questions, suggestions, or feedback? We'd love to hear from you!

DISCLAIMER & CONSENT

Purpose of data collection

- Your data will be used for project purposes within CS-MACH1.
- The collected information may be included in reports, publications, and presentations related to the project.
- If needed, your data may be shared in open-access repositories, but only in anonymized form.

Data protection & confidentiality

- All personal data will be stored securely and handled in accordance with the GDPR (EU 2016/679).
- If any personal information is collected, it will be anonymized or pseudonymized when used in project activities and research.
- Your data will not be shared with third parties beyond CS-MACH1 project partners without your additional consent.
- Your email will only be used to share relevant updates, resources, and results within the CS-MACH1 project and will not be shared outside.

Your rights

- You have the right to access, rectify, or request the deletion of your data.
- You can withdraw consent at any time without providing a reason.

36. By ticking the boxes below, you confirm that: *

Tick all that apply.

- You have read and understood this information.
 You voluntarily agree to participate.
 You understand your rights regarding your data.
 You understand that the CS-MACH1 team will use your email to share only relevant resources and results from the CS-MACH1 project to support and upscale your marine citizen science project.

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6.2. Annex 2: list of contacted projects

This annex provides the list of all projects that were contacted to participate in the survey.

"Ocean literacy" czyli przeciwko analfabetyzmowi morskemu
#2minutebeachclean
#BlackSeaMAS
#potavristou
"Blue Paths" project
5 Gyres
A CITizen science approach for data acquisition on coastal erosION
A large-scale investigation of microplastic contamination: Abundance and characteristics of microplastics in European beach sediment
A Rocha Plastics Toolbox
A scaling down mapping of <i>Pinna nobilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) through the combination of scientific literature, NATURA 2000, grey literature and citizen science data
Abundance and composition of near surface microplastics and plastic debris in the Stockholm Archipelago, Baltic Sea
Acqua di Casa Mia
Actions on Invasives
Adopt a Site - National Marine Monitoring Scheme
Adopt a Wreck
adrift
ALeRT
Algae Watch (Levävahti)
Algal Blooms Sweden
Algas na Praia
Algforskarssommar
Alien CSI Bioblitz
Alien CSI Cost Action
Alien fishes (same methodology as "Invasive Algae")
Alien invaders
AlienFish
Aliens in the Sea
All Together Global Clean Up
AlloElasmo

An Ebbing Tide...
Andromeda
ANEMONE: Marine Litter & Cetacean Monitoring
Angel Shark Project (Canarias, Wales, Greece)
Angel Shark Project: Croatia
Angel Shark Project: Greece
Angel Shark Project: Ireland
Angel Shark Project: Libya
Angel Shark Project: Wales
Angel Shark Sightings Map
Angling project: OFF THE HOOK
Animals stuck in the trash (Roskiin takertuneet elaimet)
ANM (Atlasproject Nederlandse Mollusken)
Año Nuevo Island - Animal Count
ANSWER: a scientific participatory initiative in the field of water
Antibiotic resistance in surface water and water treatment
AquaInvaders
ArcticPlastics
Artfakta
Artportalen
artsdatabank
Artsobservasjoner (Species Observations Service)
Artsobservasjoner
Assessing fish assemblages on shallow rocky reefs
Assessing the benefits of beach cleanups
Assessing the distribution and abundance of bottlenose dolphins Tursiops truncatus in Scottish waters.
Atencion No me aplastes
Atlas des amphibiens et reptiles de Bretagne
Attenti a quei 4
Attention, don't step on me!
Avez-vous vu des Mammifères marins ?
Avvistapp

Badanie obecności mezoplastiku na plażach Trójmiasta
Baltic App
Baltic Sea Project
Baltic sea project bioblitz
Baltic Seabird Project
BalticDiversity
BalticExplorer
Basking shark project
Basking Shark sighting/tags
Basking Shark Watch
Beach Cleanup Tour
Beach Explorer
Beach Track
Beached bird survey
BeachExplorer
BeachObserver
Beachwatch
Beluga Bits
Big Beach Clean
Big beach cleanup
Big Seaweed Search
Billfish Foundation Tagging
BioBlitz
Biodiversidad Virtual
BioDiversity4All
BioEcoOcean
BioLit
BioLit - A vos observations !
BioLit - Algues brunes et bigorneaux
BioLit - Attention menaces ?
BioLit - Chlorophylle-mania
BioLit - Saisons de la mer

BioLit "Nouveaux Arrivants"
BioLit, les observateurs du littoral
BioMARathon
BIOMARATO
Biomarató
BIOOBS
BioRegisto
BIOSUBZH
BioTourS
Biowatch
Bird Census
Bird Guides Sightings
Birds of the World
BirdTrack
Black Sea Watch
Bli med Under!
BLUE CONNECT: Shetland and Fair Isle IMMA
Blue Effect
Blue-Cloud 2026
Blue-Cloud Hackathon
BlueDOT
BlueLights
BODDENHECHT
Boddenhecht (Ecology and management of coastal northern pike around Rügen, Germany)
BONUS Baltic App - Wellbeing from the Baltic Sea – applications combining natural science and economics
Boskalis Beach Cleanup Tour
Bottlenose dolphins monitoring
Brand Audit - Surfers Against Sewage
British Seahorse Survey
BRIZO
Brown water (Brunt Vatten)
Building a baseline for habitat-forming corals by a multi-source approach, including Web Ecological Knowledge

Camminando sulle Tracce del Mare
Can Beach Cleans Do More Than Clean-Up Litter? Comparing Beach Cleans to Other Coastal Activities
Can citizen science contribute to fish assemblages monitoring in understudied areas? The case study of Tunisian marine protected areas
Cape Clear Bird Observatory
CapOeRa
CapOeRa-baie de Douarnenez
CapOeRa-grand public
CapOeRa-sentinelles
Capturing Our Coast
Capturing our Coast(CoCoast)
Carnet de Relevés d'Observation des Milieux Subaquatiques (CROMIS)
Case study: three Tunisian future Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and adjacent areas (framework of MedMPAnet project)
Castaway
Catshark Egg Spotting
Caulerpa cylindracea – Egadi Islands
Caulerpa cylindracea - Ligurian coast
Caulerpa taxifolia - Central Mediterranean
Caulerpa taxifolia - Mediterranean countries
Caulerpa taxifolia - Mediterranean coast France
Cephalopod Citizen Science Project
Cetacean biodiversity in the Bay of Biscay
Cetacean Recording Network
Cetacean Sanctuary Research
Cetacean Sanctuary Research - Tethys
Cetacean Strandings Investigation Programme (CSIP)
Céta'Plongée
CetaSee
CIESM Jelly Watch Program
Cigesmed for divers
circUlar Low Trophic offshore Aquaculture in wind farms and Restoration of Marine Space
Čista obala
CitClops

Citizen
Citizen Fins
Citizen Observatory Web COBWEB
Citizen Science
Citizen Science App
Citizen Science Brand Audit
Citizen Science for CIGESMED
Citizen Science Investigations - empowering the public through the use of novel technologies to collect policy-relevant marine data
Citizen Science MONitoring (CSMON) Life
Citizen Science unmanned aerial systems (UAS) and with computer vision methods for marine litter monitoring
CITIZEN SCIENTISTS NEEDED TO HELP MAP IRELAND'S MARINE LIFE
Citizen-based reporting for Marine Biodiversity in Lebanon
Citizens of Surf
Citizen-science detects the arrival and establishment of Branchiomma luctuosum (Grube, 1870) (Annelida: Polychaeta: Sabellidae) in Albania
Citizen-science mark-recapture records from 2016–17 for the Critically Endangered flapper skate (Dipturus intermedius) in Scotland
Clean & Collect
CLEAN Beach
Clean Coast Observer
Clean Sea Life
Clean Seas Odyssey
Clean Up Svalbard
Clean up the Med
CleanSea project
Climate Change (COMING SOON)
Climate fish
Climate Fish (Five minutes for climate change)
Climatescan
Cloughey and District Community Association Beach Care Group
Coastal Day (Strandens dag)
Coastal Litter Campaign
Coastal Nature Challenge
CoastSnap

CoastSnap Balears (part of the Spanish CoastSnap Network)
CoastSnap Wales
Coastwards
Coastwatch Europe
Coastwatch Ireland Coastal Survey
Co-creating strong uptake of REMEDIES for the future of our oceans through deploying plastic litter valorisation and prevention pathways
CoLab (Coastal Observing Lab in a Box)
Comber
Community Seagrass Initiative
Comparison of a Smartfin with an Infrared Sea Surface Temperature Radiometer in the Atlantic Ocean
Comptage national de la pêche à pied de loisir
Conducting an evidence-based national Non-State Actors campaign on Marine Protected Areas Network
Conservation of Marine Turtles of the Mediterranean Region
Control of wild Pacific oysters <i>Crassostrea gigas</i> within the inter-tidal zone of the North East Kent Marine Protected Areas
Coral Alert!
Coral Reef (COMING SOON)
Coral Watch
CoralWatch
Cornwall Wildlife Trust Marine Strandings Network
Corsica Alien Network
COSEA Collaboration for Effective Sea Action
CosmicSail
Cost-effective monitoring of large micro- and meso-litter in tidal and flood accumulation zones at south-western Baltic Sea beaches
Cousteau divers
CovidLitter
Crab Camouflage
Crab Watch
CROMIS
CROMIS (Carnet de Relevés d'Observations des Milieux Subaquatiques)
Crowdwater
CRUISE#SCIENCE
CSMON-Life+

CTON
CURL
Cybelle Méditerranée
Cyprus Beach Cleanup Campaigns
Człowiek – duży gatunek ssaka lądowego na plaży
Danish offshore marine mammal sighting reporting programme
Database of litter from ships
Decapod crustaceans
Decapod Crustaceans (same methodology as "Pen Shells")
Deep Sea Explorers
Deepcor
Deepod
Dem Plastikmüll auf der Spur
Dem Plastikmüll auf der Spur (Tracking Plastic Waste)
Demographic monitoring along the East-Atlantic Flyway: a case study on Sanderlings using international citizen science
Des espèces qui comptent (FFESSM)
Detecting marine litter on Arctic beaches of the Svalbard archipelago
Determining the species assemblage and habitat use of cetaceans in the Svalbard Archipelago
Diable de mer
Digging up the oceans past
Digital fishers
DIRAPO
DISCOVERY yachts
Distribution of Acantholabrus palloni in Swedish waters
Distribution of marine litter in the Moroccan Mediterranean
Distribution of plastic pellets in the Baltic Sea (PELLET)
Dive Against Debris
Dive into science
Diveboard - Scuba diving citizen science observations
Divers for the Environment: Mediterranean Underwater Biodiversity Project (N)
Divers in Northern Ireland
divers4oceanography

DNA & Liv
Dog Whelk Inventory and Monitoring
Donia
DORIS (Données d'Observations pour la Reconnaissance et l'Identification de la faune et la flore Subaquatiques)
DUGNAD
Dugnad for Havet
Duik de Noordzee schoon - ecologisch onderzoek
DutchSail
Dynamic Dunescapes
Dynamic habitat suitability modelling of black marlin
Dyreobservasjoner
Earthdive Global Dive Log
EarthEcho Water Challenge
Eastern Adriatic Monk Seal Project
eBIRD
eBlueCarbon
eBlueEconomy
eCave
ECOCEAN Whale Shark Photo Identification Library
Ecomore
ECOPredS (Ecological Consequences of Orca Predation on Seals)
ECOSEASTEM
eDisease
EDITO-Infra
EDITO-Model Lab
eDNA expeditions
Education projects - Coastal Ecosystems of Southern Portugal (Blue Carbon project)
Educational Passages Miniboat Program
eElurikkus
eFisheries
eFishKill
Egg Hunt

Eider Aware North East
eInvasive
eJellyfish
ELASMED - Citizen Participatory Observatory of the ELASmbranches of French Mediterranean
ELASMED - Observatoire participatif citoyen des ELASmbranches de MEDiterranée française
Elasmocat
eLitter
Ellenic Network on Aquatic Invasive Species
eManta
EME'RAUDE
eMPA
ENARAK
Encyclopedia of Life
Enquête EcoQo
Enquête Fulmar boréal
Enquête Mouette tridactyle
Enquête Oiseaux échoués
Enquête Oiseaux échoués (ECoQo)
Enquête oiseaux échoués Picardie
Enquête Sternes
EnviObserver
EnvLogger
eOceans
eOceans + eShark, eManta, eSeahorse, eWhale, eSeaTurtle, Marine Heatwaves, MPA Health Tracking, Marine Megafauna, etc.
ePollution
Erasmus Maris
Erasmus Maris: RAISE-CS
ESABALT - Enhanced Situational Awareness to Improve Maritime Safety in the Baltic
eSeahorse
eSeal
eSeaTurtle
eShark

ESMIC - Estimation, monitoring and reduction of plastic pollutants in Latvian-Lithuanian coastal area
Espai Mediterrani
Espèces Exotiques Envahissantes - Faune Introduite en France
Espèces Qui Comptent
Espion des grands fonds
Estimation of age at maturity of loggerhead sea turtles in the Mediterranean
Etude des Cétacés et découverte du milieu marin
European Tagged Seal Network
Evaluation de l'indice paysager sous-marin (Protocole SeaScape)
Evaluation des peuplements de poissons (Protocole FAST)
eWhale
eWhaleStranding
Expedition Grands Requins Du Bassin Algerien
Explore Océan
Explore Your Shore!
EXtreme EXposures
Eye on Earth
EyeOnWater
Falkland Islands Big Seaweed Search
FAMAR
Farmer monitoring reveals the effect of tidal height on mortality risk of oysters during a herpesvirus outbreak
Ferry Survey
FerryBox
FILMAR: Promotion of public participation in marine mammal research in areas of the Natura 2000 network
Fin whale project (Proyectos Rorcual Comun del Estrecho Oriental)
Findkelp
fischdetektive
Fish & Click
Fish Watch Forum
Fish Watchers (FishBase)
Fish&Click
Fishers' Local Ecological Knowledge Surveillance Indicators (FLEKSI)

Fishial.AI
Fishing by foot (recreative)
Fishing for Litter
Fishing in the past
Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network (FVON)
Fishmonitoring
Fiskeatlas
Fiskeatlasset
Fiskefunn
Floating Forests
Floating Litter
Flukebook
FOCCUS
Forskning på fritidsfiske
Foto-identificatie Bruinvissen Oosterschelde
FPCUP EO-Crowd
French stranding network
Fritidsfiske
from mails
From Sea to Street
Fulmar Monitoring
Funen finds Porpoises
FVON (Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network)
Fyn finder marsvin
GAP2
Gears, lost and found (Kalanpyydykset, kadonneet ja löydetyt)
Geisternetze – Falle oder Habitat
GelAvista
Geo Bon (&MBON)
Ghost Fishing
Ghost Fishing (STOP Pesca Fantasma)
Ghost Med

GIRT
Glasaalintrek
Global Earth Challenge™ Plastic Pollution
Global Fishing Watch
Global microplastic Initiative
Global Microplastics Initiative
Global Microplastics Project
Global Ocean Surface Ecosystem Alliance (GO-SEA)
Global Shark Census (COMING SOON)
GoJelly
GoJelly: a gelatinous solution to microplastic pollution
Gradanska znanost
Grand Large
Great Annual Fish Count
Great British Beach Clean
Great Nurdle Hunt
Great Shark Snapshot
Greek Shark Logbook
Green Balkan Dolphins
Green Bubbles
Green Expedition (Za?? eksped?cija)
Green Week
Grote Schelpenteldag
Grote Schelpenteldag / Big Seashell Survey
Groupe de tri de photos pour la photo-identification des dauphins de la Côte d'Emeraude
Groupe de tri de photos pour la photo-identification des dauphins de la Côte d'Emeraude.
Grup de Recerca d'Opistobranquis de Catalunya: GROC
GUILLEMOT
Gulf of Aqaba Beach Cleanups
H2020 DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea)
Häll Sverige Rent
Hanko Bird Station

HappyWhale
Harbour porpoises in north-western France
HavBlitz (SeaBlitz)
Hebridean Whale and Dolphin Trust
Hebridean Whale and Dolphin Trust: Cetacean Research Programme
Hebridean Whale and Dolphin Trust: Whale Track
Hellenic Conches
Hellenic Mediterranean Monk Seal Rescue and Information Network (HMSRINT)
Help save the Sea Cucumber
Het Groene Strand
Het Groene Strand (The Green Beach)
Hidden Deserts
Hidden Deserts - Observadores del Mar
Hippo-ATLAS
Hippo-HABITAT
Hippo-THAU - Fiche d'Observation des Syngnathidés
Hippo-THAU - Micro/Macro-habitat
Hjälp forskare att kartlägga förekomsten av Maerl på svenska havsbottnar
Hold Norge Rent
https://www.lifepinna.eu/
https://www.ornitho.cat/
Human Impacts @ coastal ecosystem
HydroColor App
Hyljehavaintoilmoitukset - LUKE
Hypogean Crustacea Recording Scheme
IAP (Invasive Alien Plants)
IAS tracker
IceWatch App
Ichtyos- Ichtyoplancton
iCoast- Did the Coast Change?
ID the Manta
Identifying cetacean species in Icelandic coastal waters

Identifying Sevengill sharks
IGENTAC
Iguanas from Above
IHO Crowd Source Bathymetry Pilot Project
IHO Crowd Sourced Bathymetry Pilot Project
Ilmoita havainto
Ilmoita kalahavainto
Image Detective
iMermaid
IMPACT-CET
iNaturalist
InfoMedusa
Infomedusa App
Initiative Ocean
InNat
Innovative modelling approaches for predicting Socio-environmental evolution in highly anthropized coastal LAGOONS
INPN Espèces (Inventaire National du Patrimoine Naturel)
INTEGRATED Digital Framework FOR Comprehensive MARITIME DATA AND INFORMATION SERVICES
International Coastal Clean Up
International Coastal Cleanup - Spain
International Coastal Cleanup by Ocean Conservancy
International Pellet Watch
International Sea Turtle Observation Registry (iSTOR)
International Waterbird Census
Internet of Turtles
Intertidal Discovery
Invader ID
Invasive Algae
Invasive Alien Species Europe App
Invasive Alien Species Tracker (IASTracker)
Invasive Species in Albanian Coast
Invazīvo sugu pārvaldnieks

Investigate marine debris (Undersøk marint avfall)
Involving recreational snorkelers in inventory improvement or creation in the Indian Ocean
Ionian Dolphin Project
iRecord
Irish Basking Shark Project
Irish Marine Recreational Angling Survey
Irish Wetland Bird Survey
Irish Whale and Dolphin Group's Ferry Surveys
Is it Alien to you.... Share it!!!
iSeahorse
iSeahorse.org
Isle of Wight Local Records Centre
Isles of Scilly - Sub-Aqua Club
iSpot
iWatch Wildlife
Järvi Meri Wiki
Järvi-merwiki
Jellyfish Alert
Jellyfish Spotting Campaign
Jellyfish Survey
Jellyfish, Rhizostoma luteum, observations in Spain
JellyWatch
Join in gulls
JONIAN DOLPHIN CONSERVATION
Kalanpyydykset, kadonneet ja löydetyt
Kduino
Keep Britain Tidy Group: National Shoreline Litter Surveys
Keep Northern Ireland Beautiful Marine Litter Survey
KelpRes
Ketos
kieler forschungs:werkstatt
Killer Shrimp Invasion Challenge

KingSearch
Klimatläroportalen "Vårt varmare hav"
Knobbed triton (Charonia lampas) monitoring project
KOR-project
KOSMOS
KOSMOS (Open Source Underwater Observation Kit)
Kuka syö rakkolevää? Vem äter blåstång?
KYMA Expeditionen
KYMA expeditions
Lagoa de Óbidos - Centro de Interpretação
Lamprey watch
Landsealot
Landshuter Black-headed gull (Landshuter Lachmöwen)
Landslide Reporter
Le suivi des traces de tortues sur les plages de pontes.
L'écovoyage d'Arvik
LEF-UOB Marine Monitoring Platform
LEPIDES Area Cantabrica
Les espèces qui comptent
Les mammifères marins de Bretagne
Les Sentinelles citoyennes
Les Sentinelles citoyennes - RIEM
LIFE European Sharks
LIFE MIGRATE Project
Life on the shore
Life On The Yealm
LifeWatch
Lighthouse coordinating and supporting the innovation ecosystem for a Healthy, Pollution free Mediterranean Sea
Limes Bubble Barrier
LIMP (Litoraal Inventaris en Monitoring Project)
Links Conservation Group
Lintuhavainnot

Lintujen rengastus
Litoral curat
LitterExplorer
Livet i fjæra
Lixo marinho app
Lobserve
Lobster fishing effort
Local Groups
Lofoten Waste Management Company (LAS) Beach Cleanups
Loodusheli
LOODUSVAATLUSTE ANDMEBAASI
Macro-déchets flottants (ObsenMer)
Macro-litter monitoring on southern Baltic beaches
Macroplastics Pollution in the Southern North Sea (Makroplastik Nordsee)
MaDCrow
MagSail
Makroplastik Nordsee
Malta Flora and Fauna app
Mammal Watch South East (MaWSE)
Mana Jūra (campaign My Sea)
Manatee Chat
Manta Matcher the Wildbook for Manta Rays
Manta rays in the Red Sea
Manx Basking Shark Watch
Manx Basking Shark Watch / Manx Whale and Dolphin Watch
Map of Life
Map the Gulf
Mapping marine litter on sandy beaches
Mapping of the algae maerl
Mapping Ostreopsis
Mapping the presence of Maerl on Swedish Seabeds
MARduino: mi boya, nuestros datos y el mar

MARIN
Marine & Beach Clean-Ups
Marine & Beach Litter Clean Ups
Marine & Beach Litter Sightings
Marine Conservation & Monitoring
Marine Creatures
Marine Debris Monitoring and Assessment Project (MDMAP)
Marine Debris tracker
Marine forests
Marine Life and Biodiversity in Lebanon
Marine Litter
Marine Litter Fulmar Monitoring (Zwerfvuil Graadmeter Onderzoek)
MARine Litter in Europe Seas: Social Awareness and CO-Responsibility (MARLISCO)
Marine Litter Monitoring Program
Marine Litter quantities on six Beaches of northern Svalbard in 2016 determined by citizen scientists
Marine Litter Watch
MARINE LITTERWATCH
Marine LitterWatch - monitoring
Marine mammals in Belgium
Marine Mediterranean Invasive Alien Species Database (MAMIAS)
Marine Mollusca of the Libyan waters, the southern Mediterranean Sea
Marine oil pollution and beached bird surveys
Marine Ranger
Marine Sportfish Tagging Programme
Marine Strandings Network Cornwall
Marine Survey Day
Marine Turtle Records
Marinexus
MarinOBS
Marins Chercheurs
Marint faunavakteri ("marine fauna watch")
Maritiem Erfgoed Texel

Maritime Hackathon
Maritime Heritage Texel
MARLIN – Baltic Marine Litter
MarLitCy
Marnoba
Marsh Explorer
Masseeksperiment 2019
MedFever
Mediterranean Fishes
Mediterranean Fishes (Change indicators)
Mediterranean Hippocampus Mission
MED-JELLYRISK
MEDLEM (MEDiterranean Large Elasmobranchs Monitoring)
MedMIS
MedObs Sub
MEDPELLETS
MedPlastic
MedusApp
Meduses.Tunisie
Meet Mee voor een schone Noordzee
MetaProbe
MeteoMeduse
Microplastic Pollution Map
Microplastic sampling in the MED
Microplastic Watchers
Microplastic Watchers (same methodology as "Marine Litter")
Migration Watch
Mikroplastik Detektive
MINKA
MINKE: Metrology for Integrated marine management and Knowledge-transfer network
MOBIDic
Monitoring and removal of lionfish, Cyprus

Monitoring Anthropogenic Particles and Plankton using Citizen Science
Monitoring bycatches of common guillemot in Sweden
Monitoring coastal biodiversity in south of Portugal
Monitoring Diel rhythms in shallow Mediterranean rocky-reef fishes
Monitoring Extreme Impacts of <i>Rugulopteryx okamurae</i> (Dictyotales, Ochrophyta) in El Estrecho Natural Park
Monitoring flapper skate through photo-identification in Scotland
Monitoring of Black Sea Cetacean Stranding Network
Monitoring of Mediterranean red coral
Monitoring of pelagic sharks in Galicia
Monitoring of poaching in Cory's Shearwater colonies
Monitoring of the macroalgal flora
Monitoring Phytoplankton by Kayak
Monitoring Sea Turtle Nesting on the Jebel Akhdar Coast
Monitoring seals and fisheries in the Clyde Sea area
Monitoring the lionfish expansion in the Mediterranean Sea
MONOCLE
Montenegro Dolphin Sightings Network
MOO (Monitoringproject Onderwater Oever)
Moray Ocean Community Invasive Speciees surveys
Mount Batten Bay Beach Clean
MPA-lobster protection areas
Multiple projects combined: Vannkvaliteten
Multiscale Observation Networks for Optical monitoring of Coastal waters, Lakes and Estuaries (MONOCLE)
My Ocean Sampling Day (OSD)
NASA NeMO-Ne
National biodiversity Network (NBN) Atlas
National Biodiversity Record Centre
National Whale & Dolphin Watch
Natura Alert
Naturæ Social Mapping
naturdive
NaturDive - Observatoire Citoyen de la Biodiversité Marine

Nature2000 sites monitoring
Naturgucker
Natusfera
NauticAttiva project
Neat beat (Siisti Biitsi)
Nederlandse Stookolieslachtoffer Onderzoek (NSO)
NEMA
Nemo Live
Nemo-Net
NeMO-Net - Gamifying 3D Labeling of Multi-Modal Reference Datasets to Support Automated Marine Habitat Mapping
NeumaticOUT
New finds, sites and radiocarbon dates of skeletal remains of the Great Auk Pinguinus impennis from The Netherlands
NEWS (non-estuarine waterbirds survey) - BTO
North East Beached Bird Surveys
North East Cetacean sightings
North Sea Cetacean Recording
North Sea Dogwhelk Survey
Northeast England Beached Bird Surveys
Norwegian Orca ID
Norwich Union Coastwatch UK
Notes from Nature - Invertebrate Time Machine
Nudibranch of Denmark
Nurseries
NZG Marine Mammal Database
O MAR DÁ BOM CLIMA
Objectif Plancton
OBSEA Expandable Seafloor Observatory
OBSEA Laboratorio Submarino
OBSenMER
Observadores del Mar
Observation des Méduses en Méditerranée
Observation Espana - Observation.es

Observation.org
Observatoire Citoyen du littoral morbihannais
Observatoire Citoyen du Littoral Morbihannais (OCLM)
Observatoire des changements de l'estran (OBCE)
Observatoire des tortues marines de Méditerranée
Observatoire FAUNA
Observatoire Participatif de la Biodiversité Marine
Observatoire Participatif des Herbiers de zostères et Syngnathidés
Observatoire Régional de la Migration des Oiseaux
Observatoire régional des oiseaux marins de Bretagne
Observatory of Marine Governance (OGMAR)
Observers App
ObsIdentify
ObsSea4Clim
Occhio alla medusa
Ocean Alert
Ocean calling
Ocean Cities
Ocean Citizen
Ocean Community Challenge
Ocean Data
Ocean Guardians
Ocean Hackathon
Ocean Initiatives
Ocean observers
Ocean Plastic
Ocean Sampling Day
Ocean Science
Ocean Travelers
Ocean Vox
OceanEye
Oceano Vox

Oceanography for everyone
OceanPlastic List
OceanWatchers
Ocrotește delfinii!
Octopus Intelligence
Octopus Intelligence - Citizen Science Project
Oddfish
Offshore wildlife sightings
Ojo a las invasoras
Olamur
Old Wheater (Whaling/Artic/WWII)
On the trail of plastic waste
Online reporting system for turtle egg theft
Open litter map
OpenTEK
Opération Cétacés Marine Mammals
Opération Méduses
Operation Otter
OPERAZIONE SQUALO ELEFANTE
OPHZ'S : Observatoire Participatif des Herbiers de zostères et Syngnathidés
Opistobranquis
ORCA Marine Mammal Surveyors
ORCA Observers
Orca Watch
Organization of marine phenology data in support of planning and conservation in ocean and coastal ecosystems
ORKS (Online Recording Kernow and Scilly)
Ornitho i NaturaList
ORNITHO.IT
OSPAR beach litter project
OSPAR Fulmar Litter Monitoring
OSPARITO
OspreyWatch

Otrivin Bottle Sightings
Otter Sightings Report
Otter Watch
Our Ocean in COVID-19
OUR OUTDOORS
Paddle Surfing for science
PaddleSurfing for Science
Pangaea Exploration
Parsac App
Participatory Ocean Color Network
PELA-Med
Pen Shells
Penguin Detective
People's Porpoise Project
Perseus Jellyfish Spotting
pH Pro
Phenomer
Photo contest "Wanted Baby Fish"
Photo identification of whales
Photo-ID catalogue
Photo-identification Porpoises Oosterschelde
PIMP (Puperslakken Inventaris en Monitoring Project)
Pinnipeds, people and photo identification: the implications of grey seal movements for effective management of the species
PI@ntnet
Plages Vivantes
Plankton i ferskvatn, Plankton i marint miljø
Plankton Planet
Plankton Portal
PlanktonID
Planteregistreringer
Plastexperimentet
Plastic Busters CAP

Plastic Busters Initiative
Plastic Litter Project: Coastal Litter Mapping
Plastic Pirates - Go Europe!
Plastic Pirates – Go Europe!
Plastic Soup Expeditions
Plastic Soup Foundation
Plastik na brzegu – nieznanne zagrożenia
PlastLIFE
PlutoF Biodiversity
POLARIS
POLARIS - Atencion Corales
POLARIS - Corbs
POLARIS - Veille environnementale
PolarQuest
Porcupine Marine Natural History Society Recording Scheme
POSEIDON - Passive-acoustic Ocean Sensor for Entertainment and Interactive Data-gathering in Opportunistic Nautical-activities
POSEIDON; Angel Shark Project
Posidonia activa
Posidonia Guards
Posimed
Posimed (Red Mediterranea de Control de la Posidonia)
Position data loggers and logbooks as tools in fisheries research
Predatory Bird Monitoring Scheme
Preventing Plastic Pollution
ProBleu
Pro-Coast
PROGRAM DE MONITORIZARE A DEȘEURILOR MARINE
Programme de photo identification des baleines à bosse de La Réunion
Programme d'études et de protection des phoques en baie de Somme
Programme national de recensement des observations de requins pèlerins
Programme Objectif Plancton à Concarneau
Project

Project Baseline
Project Biodiversity MARE Tricase
Project campaign My Sea
Project Lapwing
Project Manaia
Project Manaia - sightings
Project Noah
Project Seagrass
Projet DIRAIPO
Projet Oiseaux de France (ODF)
Projet REEHAB
Promocija birdwatchinga u FBiH
Proper Strand Lopers
Protocole ALAMER (Algues de la LAisse de MER)
Protocole OLAMER (Oiseaux de la LAisse de MER)
Proyecto ballena
Proyecto Libera
Proyectos Rorcual Comun del Estrecho Oriental
Purse Search Ireland
Pyöriäishavainnot
Qendra për Ruajtjen dhe Mbrojtjen e Mjedisit Natyror në Shqipëri
RAAlg
Rappen – rapportering av vattenorganismer
Rappen - reporting of aquatic organisms
Rapportera djur eller fågelring
Rapportera tumlare och sälar
Rarely Reported Cryptobenthic Fish in Marine Caves of the Eastern Mediterranean Sea
RecFishFuture
RECONNECT
Recording invasive species
Recording molluscs
Records of alien and a native species from Lebanon

Recreatieve zeevisserij
Recreational Catch Diaries
Recreational monitoring of marine biodiversity
Red Sea Project
RedPROMAR
Reef Alert Network
REEF CHECK FRANCE
Reef Check Med
Reef Check Tropical EcoDiver program
Reef Life survey
REEF Volunteer Fish Survey
ReefBase
Referanseflåten
ReFish
Regjistri Elektronik i Specieve Shqiptare
REGUAR (formally WANTED)
Reknotting marine biodiversity
RELIONMED
ReMed Zéro Plastique
Report a Sighting
Report an observation
Report porpoises and seals
Report Sightings/Strandings
Report the Fish/Crab Sighting (Kalahavainnot)
reSEArch-EU
Réseau Alien Corse
Réseau d'Observation des Récifs Coralliens (RORC) de Nouvelle-Calédonie
Réseau Lamproie
Réseau National Echouages
Réseau National Échouages (RNE)
Réseau Tortues Marines de Méditerranée Française
RESPIRE

Return the Tag
RISC (Recording Invasive Species Counts)
Rivages
River Tyne Kittiwake Monitoring
Rock Pool Project
Roskiin takertuneet eläimet
Royal Society for the Protection of Birds Beached Bird Survey
Run, Herring, Run!
Rydde
S.A.R.A.H.
S.E.A. (Scottish Entanglement Alliance)
Saaristolintulaskenta - LUOMUS
SAF21
Safe Sharks
SAFMC FISHstor
Sail & Explore
Sail Britain
Sailing 4 Science
Sailing for Oxygen
Sailing Hironnelle
Sailing4Ocean - Prismian Group
Sailing4Science
Salp bloom
Saltpan Recovery Project
Samen voor de aal - kruisnetmonitoring
Sampling of fish stomachs in Saltstraumen and Skjerstadfjor in northern Norway
Sandbar Shark Occurence
Sanderling project
Sandwatch
SargaSea
Save the North Sea (SNS)
Save the Waves app

Scanatura
Schelpenteldag
Schweinswale in den Flüssen Elbe und Weser
Science Gossip
Scotland's Coastal Heritage at Risk Project (SCHARP)
Scotlands coastal heritage at risk program
Scottish seashell survey
Scottish Vessel Project
Scouts4Science
SCRAPbook Project
Scuba Network
Sea Angling Diary
Sea Change
Sea Change: The European Beach Hazards Platform
Sea Deep Project
Sea Forester
Sea Guardians
Sea Sentinels - Divers United for the Environment
Sea Watch Foundation - report a sighting
Sea Watch Regular Observer
SeaBC - Birding Aboard
Seabed 2030
SeaBee
Seabird monitoring programme
Seabird monitoring programme - BTO
Seabird Soundscapes
Seabird Watch
Seabirds
Seabirds: Observations out at sea
Seabirdwatch
SeaCleaner
SeaCleaners

SeaClear 2.0
SeaClear2.0 Marine Litter Photomap
Seafloor Explorers
Seagrass Guardians
Seagrass in Reproduction
Seagrass observatory
Seagrass Spotter
Seagrass Survey
Seagrass-Watch
Seal Research Project Ireland - sightings
Seal Spotter
Seal Watch
SeaLabs
Sealife survey
Sealife tracker
SEAlly
SeaPaCS
Seaquest Southwest
Seaquest Southwest
Seasearch
Seasearch Ireland - casual recordings
SeaSearch UK
Seashore Snail Survey
Seashore Snapshot
Seashore Spotter
SEATRACK
SeaWatch-B
Seaweed and Freshwater Algae Recording
Seaweed on the Beach
Secchi App
Secchi Disk
See Science, Save Seashores (4S#)

Seguimiento de tiburones pelágicos en Galicia
SensOcean
Serpula Project
Service for the Sea
ShaREN (Shark and Ray Entanglement Network)
Shark Attract
Shark Log
Shark Observation Network
Shark Pulse
SharkApp
SharkBase
Sharkbook: The Wildbook for Sharks
sharkPulse Italia
Sharks & Rays: Vulnerable Species Protection
Sharks and Rays
SharksCount
Sharktivity
SHORE
Shorebird Research and Conservation Projects
Shoreline Monitoring Toolbox
Shoresearch
Shoresearch - North Wales
Shoresearch Cornwall
Shoresearch Devon
Shorewatch
SightMe
Siisti Biitsiin
SILLGRISLA
Silurian Research Expeditions
Sivusaalis- ja hyljehavaintoilmotukset
Skjellprøver fra laks og sjøørret
Slovenian Dolphin Project

SLOVENSKI PROJEKT ZA DELFINE
SmartBirds
Smartfin
SMARTLAGOON
SMP (Strandaanspoelisel Monitoring Project)
SMRUsealpred
Snapshots at Sea
Social Transformation for Water Stewardship through Scaling Up Citizen Science
Solent Bird Studies
Solent Waders & Brent Goose Strategy
Solent Waders and Brent Goose Strategy
Sonic Kayak
SPA/RAC
Spatio?temporal distribution of the loggerhead sea turtle in the Pelagie Archipelago
Spider Crab Watch
SPLASH-EU
Sponge Recording Project
Sponge Safari
Spoonbill Migration
Spot the Alien Fish (and other project with same methodo: spot the alien)
Spot the Jellyfish
Spot the Monk
SSI Scuba Divers
State of the World's Sea Turtles
STE - Scuba Tourism for the Environment - Red Sea Monitoring Program
Stichting the Ocean Movement
Stories & Coastal Structures
Stranding birds (ECoQo)
Stranding.nl
Strandings of NE Atlantic gorgonians
Strandspeurdag
Studland Seahorse Project

Subjective water quality monitoring, Finland
Subtidal kelp forests in Ireland
Suivi de la pêche récréative dans le Parc national de Port-Cros
Suivi des oiseaux échoués sud Baie de Somme
Suivi des populations de grandes nacres (Pinna nobilis)
Suivi des tortues marines par photo-identification
Suivi du trait de côte
Suivi Hivernal des Oiseaux Communs (SHOC)
Suivi Ichtyo-Plancton
Suivi macro-déchets
Suivi phoque sur la Canche
suivi Reef Check
Summer Arctic Landscapes With Citizen Science
Summer monitoring of baby seals
Suomen Lajitietokeskus
Suomen Partiolaiset kansalaistieteen edistäjinä (SPARKA)
Surf and clean water
Surf e água limpa
Surfer Scientist
Surfing for science
Surveillance estivale des Phoques veaux-marins
Surveillance hivernale des Phoques gris
Sustainable inland fisheries / FishSizeProject
Swymm
Syngnathids
Syngnathids (Same method as "Sharks and Rays" and "Sea Turtles")
SYNTESE (SYNgnathes TEmoins de la Santé de leur Environnement)
Tag a Tiny
Tagging coastal cod
Tagging loggerhead sea turtles in Zakynthos, Greece
Thames marine mammals sightings
The Big Beach Biodiversity

The Big Jellyfish Hunt
The Big Microplastic Survey
The Big Rock Pool Challenge
The Big Sea Survey
The Big Seaweed Search
The Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Program
The Cephalopod Citizen Science Project
The community seagrass initiative
The Conchological Society of Great Britain & Ireland Marine Mollusca Recording Scheme
The Conchological Society of Great Britain and Ireland Marine Mollusc Recording Scheme
The Danish Stranding Network
The Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network (FVON)
The GLOBE program
The Great British Beach Clean
The Great Eggcase Hunt
The Great Nurdle Hunt
The Great Shark Snapshot
The Hurtigruten Science Program
The Indigo Project (Indigo V Expeditions)
The Killer Algae Challenge
The Koster seafloor observatory
The Marine Animal Stranding Network Norway
The marine fishes of St Eustatius Island, northeastern Caribbean
The Marine Life Information Network
The Mass Experiment
The Meco Project
The National Mammal Atlas Project
the Nature and Origin of Marine Litter
The Ocean Clean Up
The Ocean Cleanup Survey App
The Ocean Movement
The ocean race Sustainable development team

The Open Air Laboratories (OPAL)
The Plastic Tide
The Ray Project
The Reference Fleet (Referanseflåten)
The Rocky Share Safari
The Secchi Disk study
The Shore thing
The Stranding Network of Schleswig-Holstein
The Stranding Program
The value of marine ecological data collected by volunteers
The Welly Zone
The Wildlife Trusts Shoresearch
There is no formal project
Tiira
T-MEDNet
TOP-HABITAT
TORSOOI
Tourism & Citizen Science - Seas, Ocean and Public Health in Europe
Track the Decade
Tracking a keystone species recovery from a mass mortality event
Tracking sharks for Conservation
Transport, weathering and pollution of plastic from container losses at sea: Observations from a spillage of inkjet cartridges in the North Atlantic Ocean
Trash Hunt
Trash Survey
TREASURE
Triskail
Trzy gatunki inżynierskie
TsiŌno
TunSea
Turtle watch 2.0
Turtle watch Egypt 2.0
Turtles Uniting Researchers and Tourists (TURT)

UK Cetacean Strandings Investigation Program
UK Tides
Un mois- un espèce (Clicnat)
Under Water Culture (Unterwasserkulturerbe)
UndercoverEisAgenten
Undersøk marint avfall
Underwater Survey Team (UST)
Unfolding Jellyfish Bloom Dynamics along the Mediterranean Basin by Transnational Citizen Science Initiatives
Unterwasserkulturerbe
UrbamarBio
UrbamarBio (Urban Beaches)
Using complementary visual approaches to investigate residency, site fidelity and movement patterns of the dusky grouper (<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>) in a Mediterranean marine protected area
Using historical and citizen science data to improve knowledge about the occurrence of the elusive sandbar shark <i>Carcharhinus plumbeus</i> (Chondrichthyes – Carcharhinidae) in the Adriatic Sea
Vårt varmare hav
Veille biologique des récifs du Prado
Vesilintulaskenta -LUOMUS
Vesitirepun avulla tuotetut havainnot vedenlaadusta
Vieraslajit.fi
Vigie des havres
Vigilancia de la Posidonia
Virtual Reef Diver
VIRTUE-s
Vismonitoring
Vogelslachtoffers
Volunteer reported catch of red-listed marine species
Volunteer Seabirds at Sea Surveys
Voyages Bio Sous-Marine
Voyages Bio Sous-Marine - protocole Fish Watch
Voyages Bio Sous-Marine - protocole micro/macro-habitat
Voyages Bio Sous-Marine - protocole présence-absence sur transects temporels
Voyages Bio Sous-Marine - recensement des poissons lessepsiens en Turquie

Waarnemingen.be / Waarneming.nl
Wadden Sea Flyway Initiative
waddenplastic.nl
Wakamewatch
Wales Coast Explorer
Walking on the Sea Traces
Walvisstrandingen
Walvisstrandingen.nl
Water front
Water Rangers
Water Rangers (in partnership with CaSTCo)
Water Sentinels
Waterline Project (in development)
Watervogeltelling
Waves of Waste
Weather Observations Website (WOW)
Weather Rescue At Sea
WeObserve
Wetland Bird Survey
Wetland Bird Survey (WeBs)
Whale Alert
Whale Alert app
Whale Chat
Whale FM
Whale mAPP
Whale project
Whale Track
Whales as Individuals
WhaleTrack Ireland
Whats out! Don't step on me! (¡Atención! ¡No me aplastes! - Kontuz! Ez nazazu zapaldu! in original languages)
What's your water level?
Where is Spooony?

Who eats bladderwrack - bridging the gap between science and society with an iconic Baltic Sea species
Wild Sea Explorer
Wildlife Observation
Wildlife sightings
Wildlife Sightings Programme
Winter gull survey - BTO
World Register of Marine Species
World Seahorse Survey
WWF Live
Yayakarsa
Yorkshire Nauralist's Union
Zajã ekspedycja
Zasoby ptaków Polski
Zeetrekellingen
Zegen in de delta
Zéro Déchet Sauvage
Zmieraczki, zanikający gatunek ziemnowodnego skorupiaka
Zwerfvuil Graadmeter Onderzoek
Καρχαρίες και Σαλάχια σε Ελλάδα και Κύπρο
Μέδουσες των ελληνικών θαλασσών
Національна мережа інформації з біорізноманіття

Annex 3: list of participating projects

This annex provides the list of all projects that took part in the survey.

EyeOnWater
Project
Greek Shark Logbook
Schelpenteldag
Grote Schelpenteldag / Big Seashell Survey
Sea Angling Diary
Seabird Watch
eOceans + eShark, eManta, eSeahorse, eWhale, eSeaTurtle, Marine Heatwaves, MPA Health Tracking, Marine Megafauna, etc.

Seabird Monitoring Programme
RECONNECT
World Seahorse Survey
BeachExplorer
ArcticPlastics
MARNOBA
Mikroplastik Detektive
Marine Litter Watch
Explore Your Shore!
iSpot
MARIN
Mana Jūra (campaign My Sea)
Sailing for Oxygen
CoastSnap Balears (part of the Spanish CoastSnap Network)
Octopus Intelligence - Citizen Science Project
LIFE European Sharks
MedFever
#Potavristou
SeaClear2.0 Marine Litter Photomap
Hebridean Whale and Dolphin Trust: Whale Track
Boddenhecht (Ecology and management of coastal northern pike around Rügen, Germany)
Hebridean Whale and Dolphin Trust: Cetacean Research Programme
PI@ntNet
Artsobservasjoner (Species Observations Service)
CosmicSail
Scottish Vessel Project
BLUE CONNECT: Shetland and Fair Isle IMMA
Solent Waders & Brent Goose Strategy
Turtle watch Egypt 2.0
Sandwatch
OSPAR Fulmar Litter Monitoring
Scuba Network

The Big Rock Pool Challenge
Conducting an evidence-based national Non-State Actors campaign on Marine Protected Areas Network
The Ocean Cleanup Survey App
Hidden Deserts - Observadores del Mar
The Conchological Society of Great Britain & Ireland Marine Mollusca Recording Scheme
Moray Ocean Community Invasive Species surveys
Water Rangers (in partnership with CaSTCo)
Observatoire Citoyen du littoral morbihannais
CoastSnap Wales
CoastSnap
The Great Eggcase Hunt
Whats out! Don't step on me! (¡Atención! ¡No me aplastes! - Kontuz! Ez nazazu zapaldu! in original languages)
BioObs
Monitoring of Black Sea Cetacean Stranding Network
Marine Litter Monitoring Program
Fiskeatlasset
The Secchi Disk study
Objectif Plancton
Seaweed on the Beach
BioEcoOcean
Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network (FVON)
TunSea
JONIAN DOLPHIN CONSERVATION
REEF CHECK FRANCE
CROMIS (Carnet de Relevés d'Observations des Milieux Subaquatiques)
Microplastic sampling in the MED
Espèces Qui Comptent
Observation.org
Stranding.nl
H2020 DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea)
Stichting the Ocean Movement
Marint faunavakteri ("marine fauna watch")

Our Outdoors
Shoresearch Devon
The Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network (FVON)
eDNA expeditions
SeaLabs
International Coastal Cleanup - Spain
NeumaticOUT
KOSMOS
Meet Mee voor een schone Noordzee
Northeast England Beached Bird Surveys
River Tyne Kittiwake Monitoring
Participatory Ocean Color Network
Distribution of plastic pellets in the Baltic Sea (PELLET)
Sailing4Science
Surfer Scientist
Erasmus Maris
CLEAN Beach
There is no formal project
MEDPELLETS
Knobbed triton (Charonia lampas) monitoring project
BioMARathon
UrbamarBio
Plages Vivantes
Posidonia Activa
TREASURE
Fish & Click
Observatory of Marine Governance (OGMAR)
PlastLIFE
ReFish
Suomen Partiolaiset kansalaistieteen edistäjinä (SPARKA)
Samen voor de aal - kruisnetmonitoring
Shoresearch

North Sea Cetacean Recording
Waves of Waste
Citizens of Surf
Happywhale
The Wildlife Trusts Shoresearch
SeaWatch-B
Shoresearch - North Wales
Database of litter from ships
Plastic Pirates - Go Europe!
Observadores del Mar
Sea Sentinels - Divers United for the Environment
Educational Passages Miniboat Program
Marine & Beach Clean-Ups

